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**Reconciling the Science of Medical
Advancements at the End-of-Life with the Art of
Dying Well**

Advocating for Legislation on Advance Decisions in Malaysia

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~Nemo Mortalium Omnibus Horis Sapit~
No Man Is At All Times Wise

Deo Gratias

For the people who accompanied me on this journey
and who made this dream become a reality:

My parents
John and Irene

My siblings
Marie and Matthew

My brothers in Christ
Timothy and Daniel

and

Trevor
an excellent programme director and supervisor
who has become a mentor and friend

+AMDG+

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List of Abbreviations

ACD	Advance Care Directive
ACP	Advance Care Planning
ADRT	Advance Decision to Refuse Treatment
AdvDecs	Advance Decisions
AdvDir	Advance Directives
AMD	Advance Medical Directive
AMDA	Advance Medical Directives Act (Singapore) 1996
CME	Code of Medical Ethics (Malaysia)
DNACPR	Do Not Attempt Cardio-Pulmonary Resuscitation
DoH	Department of Health (USA)
FDS	Flying Doctor Service
GMC	General Medical Council (UK)
GP	General Practitioner
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
LPA	Lasting Power of Attorney
LW	Living Will
MAID	Medical Assistance in Dying
MCA	Mental Capacity Act (UK) 2005
MCA CoP	Mental Capacity Act Code of Practice (UK) 2007
MHA	Mental Health Act (Malaysia) 2001
MinDef	Ministry of Defence (Malaysia)
MMA	Malaysian Medical Association
MMC	Malaysian Medical Council
MoH	Ministry of Health (Malaysia)

MoHE	Ministry of Higher Education (Malaysia)
NHS IQ	National Health Service Improving Quality
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisations
PAS	Physician-Assisted Suicide
PDA	Patient Decision Aids
POLST	Physician Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment
PSDA	Patient Self-Determination Act (USA) 1990
TCM	Traditional and Complementary Medicine
THIS	Total Hospital Information System
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
VSED	Voluntarily Stopping Eating and Drinking
WMA	World Medical Association

Abstract

Making decisions regarding care at the end-of-life is difficult for everyone involved because most patients rarely communicate their wishes for treatment beforehand. Sometimes, decisions taken by the medical team may be in conflict with the wishes of the patient or their families. This situation is more challenging in multi-cultural and multi-religious societies like Malaysia.

How can we know what treatment patients want and how are we able to be sure that we are really acting in their best interests? The answer lies in planning for our death, which firstly requires patients to have a conversation with someone else about this topic, and secondly to have it in some recorded form.

This dissertation seeks to reconcile the science of medical advancements at the end-of-life with the art of dying well by advocating for the introduction of legislation on advance decisions in Malaysia.

It commences by looking at some different forms of Advance Decisions (AdvDecs) currently available. These include the Living Will, Advance Directives, the Lasting Power of Attorney and the Physician Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment (POLST) form.

Unfortunately, there is currently no legislation pertaining to AdvDecs in Malaysia. As such, our discussion then moves on to consider current legislations on AdvDecs in the United Kingdom and Singapore, and includes some relevant legislations and guidelines in Malaysia.

An analysis of some of the medical, legal, ethical and social aspects of end-of-life care in Malaysia is then undertaken in order to help our subsequent evaluation of how AdvDecs can be of use. This sets the scene for us to determine the best possible approach to implementing AdvDecs in Malaysia.

The focus then shifts to describing the recommended step-wise approach to overcome this problem. Firstly, this is done by encouraging people to talk about their wishes and life values and secondly, to simultaneously improve the communication skills of all parties involved in end-of-life care, before the third step of legislating provisions for AdvDecs takes place.

The concluding chapters seeks to identify and examine how legislating AdvDecs in Malaysia may impact decision-making practices on end-of-life issues including the vision of shared decision-making approach and the prediction of an increase in demand for palliative care services.

Chapter 1 Introduction- The Current State of the Matter

Advances in medicine have resulted in a massive global industry that employs millions and costs billions (Le Fanu, 2011, p.xvii). On the one hand, these advances¹ have led to a global increase in life expectancy, but on the other hand they have also medicalised health to such an extent that many conditions that were once thought to be the process of natural aging are now being treated as medical diseases (Nuland, 1995, pp.xv-xvi; Gawande, 2014, pp.6-10; O'Mahony, 2016, p.4).

Frequent over-investigation and over-treatment of minor symptoms, inappropriate use of life-sustaining technologies, and the propagation of unreasonable expectations in medical practice by doctors, patients and their family members have the potential to lead to harmful consequences and outcomes (Hofmann, 2015; Hofmann, 2016; White, Ernecoff and Buddadhumaruk, 2016). Furthermore, they can also create moral distress as a result of the novel and complex ethical dilemmas that are involved, and also produce wastage of scarce health resources when faced with medical futility² (Wilmott, *et al.*, 2016).

However, despite the significant advances in medicine, death remains a certainty for every living human being. In actual fact, the medicalisation of health has also led to the medicalisation of death (Gawande, 2014, pp.6-10; Nuland, 1995, pp.xv-xvi). This

¹ Among some of the notable advances include the development of various antibiotics starting with the discovery of penicillin; the successful implementation of vaccination programs that have eradicated smallpox; and the discoveries of new techniques in transplant medicine (Le Fanu, 2011).

² According to Wilmott *et al.* (2016), the main drivers of futile treatment include patient and family requests; concerns about legal risk; doctors' professional desire to cure patients; and doctors' poor communication skills.

leads us to question if *more* is necessarily *better*, and if we may have lost the art of dying well.

A death-denying culture currently exists in Western industrialised healthcare systems where death is equated with medical failure and is hidden away or confined within the clean white walls of hospital rooms or among the machines of the intensive care unit (ICU) (Nuland, 1995, pp.xv-xvi; O'Mahony, 2016, pp.32-60). As a result of globalisation, this phenomenon has begun to slowly creep into other parts of the world including developing countries like Malaysia (Leong, 2003, p.84).

While many philosophers, theologians and bioethicists have examined questions such as '*what is a good death?*' and '*what do we need to do to achieve this good death?*' since antiquity³, our society today seems to be more fascinated with questions of '*how and when do we want to die?*' and are more focused on defending its autonomous right to determining them (Nuland, 1995, pp.265-266). Making decisions regarding care at the end-of-life is difficult for everyone involved (White, Ernecoff and Buddadhumaruk, 2016). This is not made easier in a multi-cultural and multi-religious society where a wide variety of views are held.

In the Malaysian context, Jahn Kassim and Alias (2016, p.120) write that end-of-life decision-making is "no longer confined to clinical assessments as to what would be in the best interests of the patient from a purely medical perspective, but involve due consideration of a patient's religious beliefs, customs and values, which ultimately

³ Some notable essays and publications on these topics include those of the Filipino physician, Josephine Lumitao (2001); the English clergyman, Jeremy Taylor (2007); and the Catholic saint, Robert Bellarmine (2013).

have significant influence on a patient's response to illness, suffering and dying". This is made more challenging by the fact that both Malaysian doctors and patients come from diverse cultural backgrounds and may adhere to different sets of values in accordance to their own religions. Cultural differences between the East and West also often result in a contrast between Asian and Western values (Tai and Lin, 2001; Coleman, 2012). The realisation that every individual's life experiences, values and beliefs influence the medical decision-making process, including how they think death should take place, leads us to question how we can know what treatment patients want and how we are able to be sure that we are acting in their best interests?

A common answer to this is that we need to plan for our death (Wilmott, *et al.*, 2016). The first crucial step here is for patients to have a conversation, be it between themselves and their doctor or their family members, about their wishes. The next equally crucial step is to have some form of record of these wishes. Omitting either step will result in delayed decision-making when the crucial moment arrives and possibly lead to futile treatment or other treatment that are inconsistent with the patient's wishes being provided, at least as an interim measure (*ibid.*).

As we shall discover, various forms of advance decisions (AdvDecs) both in oral and written form ranging from 'living wills' (LW) and 'advance directives' (AdvDirs) to a 'lasting power of attorney' (LPA) and more recently the 'Physician Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment' (POLST) form have been proposed. However, the term *advance decisions* is generally used in this dissertation as opposed to *advance directives* or other similar terms to emphasise the fact that while patients are able to make

decisions in advance regarding refusal of treatment, they may not direct or demand medical treatment (that healthcare professionals deem to be futile or not) in advance (Finlay, 2016). Nonetheless, until legislations are introduced to legitimise their use, any AdvDecs are technically not legally binding and may be open to dispute (Capron, 2013, pp.338-339).

Unlike in neighbouring Singapore, there is currently no legislation in Malaysia regarding the use of any form of AdvDecs (Talib, 2005). Efforts to promote the introduction of such legislations require many factors, discussed in this dissertation, to be taken into account in order to critically evaluate the best possible means by which they can be introduced to improve end-of-life care.

Capron (2013, p.337) mentions that AdvDecs are “actually a very recent response to a modern problem, namely the worry of many people that they will become victims trapped by medicine’s ever expanding ability to sustain life indefinitely after they lose the ability to voice their wishes about treatment at the end-of-life”. In attempting to provide a means for patients to determine how they wish to be treated when they are incapacitated, AdvDecs lend themselves to potential contextual influences especially as their *practical* necessities differ from their *legal* ones.

While the awareness on AdvDecs in general may still be lacking, a meta-analysis of 14 studies on physicians’ attitude towards AdvDecs revealed unanimously that physicians considered it ethically desirable to have patient input into their treatment decisions by way of AdvDecs (Coleman, 2012).

In Malaysia, doctors have also voiced a need for AdvDecs to assist them in managing their patients in a more effective manner⁴ (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a).

In response to this *need*, this dissertation seeks to determine if and how AdvDecs can be implemented in a multi-cultural and multi-religious society like Malaysia, and to examine the potential influences its implementation will have on local end-of-life decision-making practices.

Discussion in this dissertation aims to:

- (1) *Explore* some different forms of AdvDecs currently available;
- (2) *Consider* current legislations on AdvDecs;
- (3) *Study* the major factors that will influence the implementation of AdvDecs in Malaysia;
- (4) *Evaluate* the use of AdvDecs and to *determine* the best possible approach to implement AdvDecs in Malaysia; and finally
- (5) *Examine* how AdvDecs in Malaysia may impact decision-making practices on end-of-life issues.

⁴ This need stems from a few factors, including (1) concerns among religious groups in Malaysia for proper guidelines to be drafted; (2) the growth of the medical profession as a public institution; (3) the commercialisation of medical practice; (4) the increasing awareness amongst the society on medico-legal issues, and; (5) the growth of a consumerist attitude towards the provision of medical services (Jahn Kassim and Jahn Kassim, 2014).

Chapter 2 Exploring Different Forms of Advance Decisions

The principle of *respect for autonomy* is the principal idea in advocating the use of AdvDecs for end-of-life care (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009). In *Re: MB* [1997] Butler-Sloss LJ upheld that:

“a mentally competent patient has an absolute right to refuse to consent to medical treatment for any reason, rational or irrational, or for no reason at all, even where that decision may lead to his or her own death”.

The most common arguments for AdvDecs seek to ensure that mentally competent patients are provided with the means to continue exercising their autonomy when they no longer possess decision-making capacity (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009).

The cause for AdvDecs has also thrived alongside the struggle for the prominence of autonomy in favour of *medical paternalism*⁵. While it is arguable that AdvDecs ultimately contribute to the patient’s good because patients are entitled to refuse treatments they consider to be more harmful than helpful to them, doctors too have professional responsibilities to carry out and patients cannot assume that they are mere technicians whose duties are to comply with every patient’s request (*ibid.*).

⁵ The main argument against medical paternalism being that doctors cannot and will never be able to know enough about their patient’s values, wants, needs, interests, hopes and fears in order to make what patients consider to be correct decisions for them all the time (Jahn Kassim, Alias and Muhammad, 2014).

It has also been noted that dying patients do not necessarily move sequentially through Kubler-Ross' five neat stages of grief⁶ (O'Mahony, 2016, p.121). What this means is that patients may change their views on treatment options as they progress towards the acceptance of their mortality. While no unanimity has been reached among experts about the role and utility of AdvDecs, proponents for them highlight the flexibility they possess to cater to the changes patients experience that makes them an effective mechanism not only to facilitate religious and spiritual awareness in end-of-life care, but also as a means whereby ethical and social implications can be "anticipated and acted upon in advance rather than *post factum*" (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2016, p.131). Some proponents for AdvDecs have even gone as far as to propose that they should be made compulsory for every patient (Gawande, 2016a).

While variations may exist among different AdvDecs currently available, they all often include the following features (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009, p.225-6):

- (1) a valid form (written and signed statement, presence of witnesses),
- (2) not being contrary to the law,
- (3) the factual correspondence between the circumstances at the time of implementation of the AdvDecs and the situation envisaged by the patient at the time of writing them,
- (4) the time validity and absence of revocation of the document,
- (5) conformity to good clinical practice,
- (6) the best interests of the patient.

⁶ Elizabeth Kubler-Ross (1970), an American psychiatrist, proposed 5 stages of grief in her book *On Death and Dying*, commonly remembered by the acronym DABDA. She proposed that patients generally go through stages of *denial*, *anger*, *bargaining*, *depression* before coming to *acceptance* of the fact that they are dying.

According to Gawande (2014, p.259), the vital questions that are considered in AdvDecs are also largely the same and revolve around:

- (1) What is your understanding of the situation and its potential outcomes?
- (2) What are your fears and what are your hopes?
- (3) What are the trade-offs you are willing to make and not willing to make?
- (4) What is the course of action that best serves this understanding?

2.1 Living Will (LW)

An American lawyer introduced the first form of AdvDecs, termed as the *living will*, in the 1960's (Kutner, 1969). However, this concept did not garner much support until 1976 when the first LW law in the United States of America (USA) was passed in California (Meilaender, 1995). Since then, most states in the USA have enacted laws to give legal standing to LWs.

The LW is a written document that allows patients to give instructions for medical care in their final days of life in exactly the same way as a *will* functions as a document for people to leave instructions on how to dispose of their estate after death (Capron, 2013, p.337). Its purported benefits include liberating anxious relatives and diffident doctors from the requirement of decision-making; allowing currently competent patients to participate in future treatment decision-making for care when they have lost their capacity; and most importantly, educating healthcare providers of the public's sense that life-prolonging treatment may not always be regarded as good⁷ (Capron, 2013, p.338).

⁷ Capron (2013, p.339) uses the famous case involving an American girl, Karen Quinlan, to illustrate this when he writes that "the ultimate horror is not death, but the possibility of being maintained in limbo in a sterile room, by machines that are controlled by strangers".

Currently, the term *living will* is used in place of or towards the same end as *advanced directives* (Coleman, 2012). In the beginning however, the original LW and other similar documents that followed its language, faced a major limitation in that they lacked legal effect under the common law of agency (Capron, 2013, p.338). However, since the passing of the Patient Self-Determination Act (PSDA) (USA) 1990 in the USA, hospitals have been required to advise patients on admission regarding their right to establish AdvDecs, which include LWs (Meilaender, 1995).

A common criticism of the LW concerns the difficulty patients face in attempting to predict the choices they want in the absence of a diagnosis or specific disease when drawing up this document⁸. This commonly results in the original LWs being drafted in vague or ambiguous terms in order to attempt to cover a variety of circumstances that were yet unbeknown to them⁹, making their application in real clinical scenarios very difficult (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009).

Lastly, while the ‘not legally binding’ excuse in some sense hindered the true usefulness of LWs as it was not able to dispel physicians’ liability fears, there were also others who feared that LWs could be misused by doctors or family members to neglect providing adequate care for some patients (Cortes, 2015).

⁸ For “how can healthy individuals decide in advance in sufficiently specific terms the treatments that they would like to have or not, without knowing the particular circumstances in which they will be placed?” (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009, p.209). This quote highlights the point that in some circumstances LWs may not fulfil the requirement for an informed consent.

⁹ Critics of the LW have mentioned that the documents were often written generically, either employing poetic language (such as ‘heroic measures’) or wording that raises more questions than it answers (such as ‘means that only prolong the dying process’) (Capron, 2013, p.340).

2.2 Advance Directives (AdvDirs)

Based on a similar concept to the LW, AdvDirs¹⁰ consist of a variety of written instructions that allows a competent individual to state in advance of becoming incompetent his or her wish to accept or forgo a particular medical treatment in a future instance when they are no longer mentally competent (Robertson, 1995).

The Mental Capacity Act (MCA) (UK) 2005 refers to these anticipatory decisions as ‘advance decisions’ and in Singapore they are referred to as ‘advance medical directives (AMD)’¹¹. They are also sometimes known as ‘advanced decisions to refuse treatment’ (ADRT) based on the earlier mentioned concept that one cannot direct (or demand) someone else in advance for treatment, but can make an advanced decision to refuse it.

According to Capron (2013, p.337), in the USA

“advance directives arose initially as a response to the decision-making paralysis, born of guilt and uncertainty, that often occurs when the question is whether to forgo the medical interventions sustaining the life of someone who is no longer able to make his or her own views known.”

This again culminated with the enactment of the PSDA(USA) 1990 that legalised and popularised the use of AdvDirs in the USA and beyond. Currently, most countries in the western hemisphere have AdvDirs-specific laws (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009; Coleman, 2012).

¹⁰ See Appendix A for an example of an Advance Directive.

¹¹ This is the term used in the Singaporean Advance Medical Directive Act (AMDA) 1997.

In the United Kingdom (UK), an ADRT can only be made by someone over the age of 18 who has the mental capacity to do so (National Health Service Improving Quality (NHS IQ), 2014b). Both verbal or written forms are acceptable, but if it includes the refusal of life-sustaining treatment, this must be done in writing, signed, witnessed and include the words '*even if life is at risk*' (MCA(UK) 2005, s25.5a). ADRTs only come into effect when the individual loses capacity and relates to refusal of specific treatment in specifically identified circumstances. If an ADRT is deemed to be valid, it is legally binding to everyone involved in the care of the individual and applicable under the requirements of the MCA(UK) 2005¹².

The making of an ADRT is voluntary and patients should not be coerced or pressurised to make them. While the responsibility for making an ADRT lies with the person making it, the MCA Code of Practice (MCA CoP) (UK) 2007 (s.9.3) states that before healthcare professionals can apply an ADRT, there must be proof that the decision exists, is valid and is applicable to the current circumstances. It is also the responsibility of the person making the ADRT to ensure that their decision will be drawn to the attention of healthcare professionals when it is needed (MCA CoP(UK) 2007, s.9.38). These decisions that comply with the requirements of the MCA(UK) 2005 (s.26.1) have the same legal standing as refusals of treatment made by patients with capacity.

¹² An ADRT can however be overridden by the Mental Health Act (UK) 2007, but only for psychiatric treatment.

The level of detail required may complicate the creation of sufficiently specific ADRT unless somebody has already been diagnosed with a particular condition¹³ (NHS IQ, 2014b, p.10). Moreover, only advance decisions to *refuse* treatment can be made as the MCA CoP(UK) 2007 clearly states that “nobody has the legal right to demand specific treatment, either at the time or in advance” (s.9.4), and “nobody can ask for and receive procedures that are against the law” (s.9.5) and ADRTs also cannot be used to refuse basic comfort and care.

Even if healthcare professionals may judge an apparent ADRT to not be legally binding, the decisions stipulated in the ADRT should not be completely ignored and should still be taken into account when determining the best interests of the said patient. Where healthcare professionals may disagree in principle with patients’ decisions to refuse life-sustaining treatment, the guideline specifies that they are not compelled to act against their beliefs but must also “consequently not simply abandon patients or act in a way that affects their care” (MCA CoP(UK) 2007, s.9.61).

Seeking advice from healthcare professionals or organisations is recommended not only to ensure that adequate support can be given about the process of how to make an ADRT, but can also be a helpful opportunity to discuss the person’s future care and treatment¹⁴. (NHS IQ, 2014b, p.5).

¹³ This is because once there is a diagnosis, it will be easier to anticipate specific events on the disease pathway that may give rise to a specific treatment decision.

¹⁴ While it is recommended that people who are thinking of making an ADRT seek professional assistance to help them, it is up to the person whether they want to do this or not.

Finally, the MCA(UK) 2005 allows patients who have made AdvDecs to cancel their decisions, or part of them, at any time (s.24.3), and also includes the possibility of appointing a proxy who is authorised to make healthcare decisions on the person's behalf (s.25.7).

2.3 Lasting Power of Attorney (LPA)

The LPA is a provision for individuals (termed '*donor*') to appoint someone else as their healthcare proxy (termed '*donee*' or '*attorney*') to make healthcare-related decisions on their behalf when they lose the ability to do so (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009, p.208).

LPAs differ from LWs in that they allow the donee to replace the incapacitated donor in medical decision-making while LWs are merely considered an expression of the patient's wishes and preferences (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a). LPAs also provide a personal voice for clarifying the patient's preferences when they have been formulated in ambiguous terms, and to deal with unexpected developments that had not been specifically addressed by the patient (*ibid.*).

Under the provisions of the MCA(UK) 2005, patients have the options of choosing to make an ADRT or a LPA (s.25). The LPA can apply to health and welfare, or property and affairs, but only the former are able to make healthcare decisions¹⁵ (NHS IQ, 2014a). In addition, a LPA must be made in a prescribed form and be registered with the Office of the Public Guardian (*ibid.*). According to the MCA CoP(UK) 2007, the

¹⁵ However, when the healthcare decisions involve life-sustaining treatment, the donee is only allowed to make these decisions if this has been specifically allowed in the LPA document.

decisions made by the donee will supersede those of an ADRT if the LPA was appointed after a prior ADRT was made, and the contrary also holds true (s.9.34).

In Malaysia, the existing Powers of Attorney Act 1949 regulates normal powers of attorney that are revocable upon the death, unsoundness of mind or bankruptcy of the donor, while provisions dealing with an irrevocable power of attorney are relevant to only property transactions, and are incompatible with the nature of a LPA as we have described here (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a).

2.4 Advance Care Planning (ACP)

Cicely Saunders¹⁶ who established St Christopher's in London as the first modern hospice in 1967 is also widely credited to be one of the founders of palliative care as a branch of medicine (O'Mahony, 2016, pp.118-119). Since then palliative care has advanced and emerged as an essential part of medical care that is defined as "an approach that improves the quality of life of patients and their families facing the problem associated with life-threatening illness, through the prevention and relief of suffering by means of early identification and impeccable assessment and treatment of pain and other problems, physical, psychosocial and spiritual" (World Health Organisation, 1946). In Malaysia, palliative care services were first introduced in late 1991 and have also grown since then (Leong, 2003).

ACP is an essential part of palliative care described as "a voluntary process of discussion and review to help an individual who has capacity to anticipate how their

¹⁶ She initially trained as a nurse but subsequently qualified as a doctor after she took the advice of a surgeon to study medicine if she really wanted to work with the dying because it was doctors 'who deserted the dying' (O'Mahony, 2016, p.118).

condition may affect them in the future and, if they wish, set on record choices about their care and treatment and/or an advance decision to refuse a treatment in specific circumstances, so that these can be referred to by those responsible for their care or treatment (whether professional staff or family carers) in the event that they lose capacity to decide once their illness progresses” (NHS IQ, 2014a, p.6).

It is a process provided for and regulated by the MCA(UK) 2005 and Figure 1 gives a graphic representation of this relationship and the four possible formalized outcomes of ACP:

Figure 1- Advance Care Planning (NHS IQ, 2014a, p.8)

The major difference between ACP and normal care planning is that ACP can only involve someone with capacity to decide and that it usually takes place in the context of an “anticipated deterioration in the individual’s condition in the future” resulting in

the loss of capacity¹⁷ (NHS IQ, 2014a, p.23). This usually takes place at one of the following key points in the individual's life (*ibid.*, p.25):

- (1) Following a new diagnosis of a life-limiting condition;
- (2) When there is a significant shift in treatment focus;
- (3) At the time of an assessment of the individual's needs; or
- (4) Following multiple hospital admissions.

ACP may include requirements or advance statements stating an individual's wishes and preferences, beliefs and values about what should be done when they become incapacitated. This is similar to a LW and must be taken into account as part of an overall best interests judgment but are *not* legally binding (NHS IQ, 2014b). Similarly, it may also include an ADRT that is legally binding.

The main benefit of ACP is derived from the *discussion process* between doctors, patients, caregivers, and their family members to develop and document a valid projection of the patient's wishes regarding their medical care (Htut, Shahrul and Poi, 2007). This family meeting can be considered as a procedure, and requires "no less skill than performing an operation" (Gawande, 2014, p.131). It provides an assurance for patients that healthcare decisions will conform to their wishes and interests, and help to alleviate the psychological burden experienced by both family members and healthcare providers (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a). In addition, studies have also demonstrated that ACP discussions have helped patients to experience an increased sense of control and hope (Davison and Simpson, 2006), and to perceive that their relationships with others are stronger especially since patients are able to anticipate

¹⁷ That being said, either the individual or a care provider can initiate ACP at any time.

the sorts of decisions that may need to be made in the trajectory of their disease progression and this in turn can facilitate timely transitions to palliative care, bringing an improved sense of satisfaction with end-of-life care for bereaved carers (Brinkman-Stoppelenburg, Rietjens and van der Heide, 2014). Unfortunately, there are some people who may experience negative outcomes from ACP, especially those who feel their coping styles challenged or those who are not yet ready to think about their illness and future (NHS IQ, 2014a, p.24).

2.5 Physician Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment (POLST)

The POLST form¹⁸, that is intended to be a medical order, is known by at least 14 different names in the USA, and is currently being established¹⁹ in almost all states due to the perceived limited success²⁰ of traditional AdvDirs in the American setting (Pope and Hexum, 2012).

However, it is meant to *supplement* and not *replace* traditional AdvDirs as a tool that helps to provide a framework for end-of-life care conversations for patients expected to die within the next year (*ibid.*). Among the advantages of the POLST form highlighted by Pope and Hexum (2012, p.354) include that:

- (1) it is written on a single-sheet, standardized form that is easy to follow;

¹⁸ See Appendix B for an example of a POLST Form.

¹⁹ The implementation of POLST in the USA has generally been done through one of the following four methods: (1) authorisation by statute; (2) by administrative regulations; (3) relying on informal guidelines and clinical consensus; or (4) by an incremental approach.

²⁰ According to Pope and Hexum (2012), this includes the fact that not many patients have completed an AdvDir, and that most of the AdvDirs that have been completed are unavailable when needed (especially when treatment involves a different institution from where the AdvDirs have been made). In addition, the vague terminology and need for AdvDirs to be reduced into medical orders have also contributed to this.

- (2) there is no need for interpretation and translation because POLST is an immediately actionable medical order;
- (3) it is brightly coloured for easy identification; and
- (4) it is easily transportable, remaining in the patient's charts and travelling with the patient from hospital to nursing home, thus helping to streamline the transfer of patient records between facilities.

In addition, the POLST form addresses an entire range of life-sustaining treatments like cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR), intravenous fluids, antibiotics, a feeding tube, and artificial breathing (*ibid.*). In this way, POLST proponents claim that it clarifies treatment intentions and minimises confusion about patient preferences while assisting the healthcare team in promoting patient autonomy.

A POLST is usually created with a healthcare provider at or near the time when an acute or serious chronic condition develops (*ibid.*). It addresses the patient's current situation and not a possible future scenario. This results in a greater chance that the patient's decision will be more informed and relevant to the specific medical situation at hand. It also ensures that the decisions taken are more likely to be made known when a decision is required and improves compliance by healthcare providers.

Parallel to the duty under the PSDA(USA) 1990, some states in America have required hospitals or long-term care facilities to *offer* POLST to certain groups of patients but no state requires a patient to *complete* it as POLST is based on the voluntary, informed consent of a patient. Unfortunately, this *mandatory offer* has sometimes

been misinterpreted to mean that all patients *must have completed* a POLST form (Pope and Hexum, 2012).

2.6 Others

The two main ways provided by the MCA(UK) 2005 for someone to prepare in advance to determine end-of-life decisions, as we have seen, are the LPA and the ADRT. While some physicians advocate the use of specific forms with a precise checklist of interventions for patients to choose (like the POLST) in order to avoid arguments over what they would have wanted, other physicians object with the argument that the most important factors are not the means that are offered, but the end result produced- that is, if recovery is achieved or whether the treatment will cause further pain and dehumanisation of the dying process (Capron, 2013, p.340).

Some experts regard *appointment-type directives* such as the LPA more useful than an *instruction-type directive* like the LW²¹ while others have proposed that patients should instead have a written document of values that they subscribe to or something that would link issues encountered in the dying process with the way of life of that particular person (*ibid.*). Wyatt (2015, p.146) highlights the fact that the MCA(UK) 2005 also has specific provisions for people to write a statement of their wishes, feelings and values while they still have the capacity to do so. Even though this statement may not be legally binding, it must be considered by medical teams, attorneys and is particularly helpful in assisting in determining one's best interests.

²¹ Wyatt (2015, p.146) points out that this requires the assumption that (1) patients have someone they can trust to be their proxy, (2) that the proxy is available at the time of need, and (3) that the proxy does not mind making those decisions for the patient.

This *Statement of Wishes and Values* has no specific format but an example from Wyatt's book, *Right to Die* (2015), can be found in Appendix C.

Lastly, another initiative worthy of mention here that is based on the oral tradition is *The Conversation Project* (2016). It is a project to transform the death-denying or hiding culture where people do not want to talk about dying to one where people are comfortable talking about their own mortality. Started by Ellen Goodman in the USA in 2010 and supported by others who shared similar experiences of 'good' and 'bad' deaths, it aims to help people talk about their wishes for end-of-life care starting at the kitchen table with their loved ones (*ibid.*). Starter-kits and testimonials are provided in order to facilitate this conversation that can be initiated by the dying person or their loved ones. While this conversation may not be legally binding in some countries, it may be possible to consider this as a verbal ADRT in others. Ultimately, its goal is to attempt to get people to achieve Kubler-Ross' *acceptance* phase and to provide all parties involved in end-of-life decision-making with a useful platform to base their decisions on²².

²² Numerous authors on end-of-life matters including Wyatt (2015, p.148) have also mentioned that ultimately, the greatest importance may be to have conversations with our close relatives and friends in advance of the crisis.

Chapter 3 Considering Current Legislations

3.1 United Kingdom

The main legislation in the UK that legitimises AdvDecs for end-of-life care is the MCA(UK) 2005 that came into force on 1 October 2007, which is supported and is to be read together with the MCA CoP(UK) 2007²³. Reference must also be made to the Explanatory Notes on the MCA(UK) 2005²⁴. In addition to these, Appendix D lists other Guidance and Safeguards pertaining to end-of-life care that have been issued by other relevant authorities.

According to Wyatt (2015, p.142), many relatives still mistakenly believe that they have the legal right or duty to make medical decisions on behalf of the dying patient regardless of the patient's capacity. He points out that the MCA(UK) 2005 states that if the patient still has legal capacity, then it is entirely up to that individual to decide if they want their relatives and carers to be involved in determining their care, and the extent to which this should be done.

As previously mentioned, the principle of respect for autonomy applies to patients with capacity even if the decisions chosen do not coincide with the opinions of the medical team (Keown, 2015). In this respect, the MCA(UK) 2005 also spells out the legal framework to be followed when assessing capacity that consists of applying a

²³ The *Code of Practice* supports the legal framework provided by the MCA(UK) 2005 and acts as a guidance as to how the provisions of the latter are to be implemented.

²⁴ The reference is prepared by the Department for Constitutional Affairs and the Department of Health, and is intended to assist the understanding of certain provisions of the statute.

two-stage test alongside a prohibition against making superficial judgments about capacity²⁵.

If the person loses capacity, the MCA(UK) 2005 then delegates the legal responsibility for treatment decisions to the treating doctors²⁶. The determining principle also changes its focus to the determination of the *patient's best interests* (MCA(UK) 2005, s1.5). To this extent, the MCA(UK) 2005 also provides for the appointment of a healthcare proxy through a LPA, or for patients to make ADRTs while they still have capacity. If the patient has none of these, the healthcare team then has a duty to consult the patient's next-of-kin, and other relatives and carers, as part of the process laid down by the said Act (s.4.6), which is as follows:

- (1) Determining the past and present wishes and feelings of the patient;
- (2) Determining the beliefs and values that would be likely to influence the patient's decision if they had capacity; and
- (3) Determining any other factors that the patient would be likely to consider.

3.2 Singapore

Singapore is a multi-cultural and multi-religious state similar to Malaysia. The country was once upon a time, a part of the British Straits Settlement. Later, it became a part of Malaysia (1963-1965) before achieving independence. It is currently run as a secular state, having no official religion. Besides inheriting the common law legal

²⁵ The first stage is diagnostic, asking the question 'does the person have an impairment of the mind or brain?', which means that they are unable to make a decision for themselves. The second stage then is functional whereby the person is unable to make a decision for themselves if they cannot understand, retain use, or weight relevant information about the treatment, or if they are unable to communicate by any means (MCA CoP(UK) 2007, s4.11-4.25).

²⁶ This lies in particular with the doctor who carries overall responsibility for her or her care- in the hospital setting, this is usually a named consultant.

system, Singapore also enacted the Advance Medical Directive Act (AMDA) in 1996 and the Mental Capacity Act (Singapore) in 2008 to legislate decision-making at the end-of-life (Menon, 2012).

The AMDA(Singapore) 1996 allows competent persons over the age of 21 years to make an AMD specifically if they desire “not to be subjected to extraordinary life-sustaining treatment in the event of suffering from a terminal illness” (s.3.1). The AMD must be witnessed by two people, one of whom is a medical practitioner and must be written on a prescribed form and registered in the register of AMDs (AMDA(Singapore) 1996, s.3.2, 5.1). However, while the AMD can be revoked at any time, be it in writing, orally, or in any other manner that the patient is able to communicate in, the revocation must be notified to the Registrar in writing (*ibid.*, s.7).

A couple of points that are particular to the AMDA(Singapore) 1996 are discussed here. The first is the fact that the provision for AMDs is very much focused on the diagnosis of a *terminal illness*. Specific procedures are given in Section 9 as to how this diagnosis is made including the medical practitioners who are eligible to certify the diagnosis. The second is that Section 10.6 specifically prohibits the withholding or withdrawing of extraordinary life-sustaining treatment from “a patient known to the medical practitioner to be pregnant so long as it is probable that the foetus will develop to the point of live birth with continued application of extraordinary life-sustaining treatment”, and the third is that Section 11 specifically mentions that AMDs do not apply to palliative care measures. It also mentions that an AMD should not affect insurance policies, and that for the purposes of law, the withholding or

withdrawing of treatment shall not constitute a cause of death if it was “a result of and in compliance with a directive validly made” (AMDA(Singapore) 1996, s.20.1).

According to Menon (2012), another peculiarity of the Singaporean AMDA lies in Section 15 that makes it an offence for the medical practitioner to enquire from a patient whether an AMD has previously been made²⁷. Lee (2016) explains that in current medical practice, the patient makes his or her wishes known to the doctor for an AMD, and this is then formalised through the prescribed paperwork and the procedures provided for in the AMDA(Singapore) 1996. However, if the patient has mental capacity and is admitted to the hospital in the future, the Act prevents the caring physician to initiate and ask the patient whether he or she has an AMD. The doctor instead has to enquire from the relevant authorities regarding this, which involves a multi-step process that can only be done under certain conditions. As such, he argues that an AMD is of limited utility value in Singapore because when patients are already at the stage where AMDs can be applied, best interests can easily determine if curative or palliative care should be provided and this provision, under the MCA(Singapore) 2008 takes precedence over the AMDA(Singapore) 1996 (Lee, 2016).

3.3 Malaysia

Despite being a former British colony and inheriting the common law system like Singapore, Malaysia does not currently have any legislation regarding the use of any form of AdvDecs for end-of-life care. Medical practice in Malaysia is currently

²⁷ It is likely that the AMDA(Singapore) 1996 is the only act in the world currently to have this clause prohibiting doctors from enquiring if patients have made an AMD.

governed by the Medical Act (Malaysia) 1971²⁸ and the Medical Regulations (Malaysia) 1974²⁹. In the private healthcare setting, the additional Private Healthcare Facilities and Services Act (Malaysia) 1998 also needs to be adhered to.

Active euthanasia is currently not permitted in Malaysia and the provisions for punishment of this crime are provided in the Penal Code (Revised 1997). At the same time, *passive euthanasia* in the form of withholding and withdrawing treatment is more of a problem because of the multi-cultural and multi-religious nature of the Malaysian society (Talib, 2002).

In discussing passive euthanasia, Sections 299 and 306 of the Penal Code are relevant legal provisions. Section 299 states that “whoever causes death by doing an act with the intention of causing death or with the intention of causing such bodily injury as is likely to cause death, or with the knowledge that he is likely by such act to cause death, commits the offence of culpable homicide”. Talib (2005) proposes that the word *act* extends to illegal *omissions*. If omissions, such as withholding and withdrawing treatment, are deemed illegal under Malaysian law, then passive euthanasia would amount to a criminal offence according to the Code. However, she claims that these do not amount to illegal omissions and therefore passive euthanasia is not an offence under Section 299.

²⁸ At the time of writing, there exists an alternative Medical (Amendment) Act (Malaysia) 2012. The amended Act received the Royal Assent on 5 September 2012 and was published in the Malaysian Gazette on 20 September 2012 but has yet to come into force.

²⁹ The Medical Regulations (Malaysia) 1974 provides the necessary statutes for the setting up of the Malaysian Medical Council (MMC), and subsequently the duties of the MMC to govern the licensing of medical practitioners and to conduct disciplinary proceedings against any registered medical practitioner.

With regards to Section 306, which provides for the offence of abetment of suicide, Talib (2005) argues that the Malaysian courts view the requests of terminally ill patients in Malaysia for treatment to be withdrawn or withheld as a wish to be discharged home or because of futility of treatment and therefore this Section would be inapplicable. According to her, “if the patient dies after treatment is withdrawn or withheld, the cause of death would be their illness and not suicide” (Talib, 2002, p.609). Some similarities can be drawn here with Section 20.1 of the AMDA(Singapore) 1996³⁰.

Another piece of potentially relevant Malaysian legislation lies in the Mental Health Act (MHA) (Malaysia) 2001. However, it does not cover all instances of incapacity and only applies to those with a ‘mental disorder’ as defined in Section 2.1³¹. Jahn Kassim and Alias (2015a, p.13) also clarify that this statute “is not meant to cover situations in which a person temporarily loses consciousness or where his cognitive functions are impaired due to medical conditions other than mental illness”. In addition, the MHA(Malaysia) 2001 does not talk about the applicability of AdvDecs for situations where the mentally disordered person is incapable of giving consent and the principle of best interests is not specifically mentioned as a consideration for consent given by persons authorised to do so on behalf of the patient (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a).

³⁰ Section 20.1 states that “for the purposes of the laws of Singapore, the non-application of extraordinary life-sustaining treatment to, or the withdrawal of extraordinary life-sustaining treatment from, a person suffering from a terminal illness shall not constitute a cause of death where the non-application or withdrawal was a result of and in compliance with a directive validly made in accordance with this Act by the person”.

³¹ According to Section 2.1, “‘mental disorder’ means any mental illness, arrested or incomplete development of the mind, psychiatric disorder or any other disorder or disability of the mind however acquired”.

Local legal scholars are of the opinion that while no cases regarding AdvDecs have at present been brought to the Malaysian judiciary for resolution, the reliance on common law will be a significant influence in any decision made if such a case were to be brought before the courts³² (Talib, 2005). This however, will also need to take into consideration the local values and customs in Malaysia.

Two additional pieces of guidance will be mentioned in our discussion here. The first is the *Code of Medical Ethics (CME) 2001* of the Malaysian Medical Association (MMA) where a general mention of AdvDirs is alluded to in Section 2.5 which states that in the case of a dying patient, “one should always take into consideration any advance directives and the wishes of the family in this regard”³³. The second is the Malaysian Medical Council (MMC) guidance *Consent For Treatment of Patients by Registered Medical Practitioners 2016* where a brief reference is made to *advance care directives* or *living wills* in Section 18. However, it remains unclear how these guidelines can be effectively carried out in practice, at least in terms of seeking the legal validity of AdvDirs, due to the paucity of clear, precise and enforceable legal standards on the matter in Malaysia (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a).

³² This is in accordance with Section 3 of the Civil Law Act (Malaysia) 1956 that allows Malaysian courts to apply the common law of the UK and rules of equity where no provision on the subject matter has been made by any written law in Malaysia.

³³ The CME also makes reference to numerous declarations and statements made by international bodies such as the World Medical Association (WMA) including the 1983 WMA Declaration of Venice on Terminal Illness.

Chapter 4 Studying Major Influencing Factors

4.1 The Malaysian Context

The use of AdvDecs in the Malaysian healthcare setting remains a novel concept and this chapter aims to discuss the factors that will play a significant part in deciding how to implement them in Malaysia. Its novelty can be primarily attributed to the cultural conditions and lack of exposure on the subject matter in the local setting (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a).

An overview of the country is given in order to understand how some of these factors interact with each other, taking into account the complexities and uniqueness of the situation in Malaysia.

The Federation of Malaya, constituting nine Malay states and two of the British Straits Settlements achieved independence from the British Empire on 31st August 1957. In 1963, the states of Sabah and Sarawak in Borneo, and Singapore joined the federation to form Malaysia. However, due to disagreements between the Malaysian Central Government and the Singaporean State Government on numerous aspects, Singapore eventually seceded in 1965, resulting in the present Malaysia constituting of 13 states. Figure 2 helps to illustrate this graphically:

Figure 2- Map of Malaysia (Divezone, 2012)

Malaysia, a member of the British Commonwealth, boasts a multi-cultural, multi-ethnic and multi-religious state, with the government system largely modelled on the Westminster parliamentary system. The Federal Constitution is the highest law of the land and a constitutional monarchy system is implemented where the King, known as the Yang Di-Pertuan Agong, is rotated among the rulers of the original nine Malay states for a fixed 5-year period each.

Different ethnicities make up Malaysia's population, with Malays (67.4%) being the largest ethnic group, followed by Chinese (24.6%), Indians (7.3%) and other ethnicities (0.7%) (Leong, 2003). Data from the latest Housing and Population Census of Malaysia reveals that Islam (61.3%) is the majority religion in the country, followed by Buddhism (19.8%), Christianity (9.2%) and Hinduism (6.3%) while only 3.4% of Malaysians practiced other or no religions (Department of Statistics

(Malaysia), 2010). While the Federal Constitution enshrines Islam as the state religion, it also guarantees the freedom of other religions.

The *legislative* power is divided between the federation and the states, while the *executive* power is given to the Federal Ministerial Cabinet, led by the Prime Minister. A unique dual-justice system exists, comprising of the Civil and *Syariah*³⁴ law, where the *Syariah* court deliberates on matters regarding Islam and its teachings on marriage, inheritance, divorce and apostasy among others and is only binding to Muslims (Dahlan and Faudzi, 2015).

As mentioned, there are currently no laws in Malaysia that specifically regulate the usage of any form of AdvDecs for decision-making on end-of-life care, and published resources on this topic remain scarce. However, two recent articles regarding end-of-life decision-making in the Malaysian context have been published, and their findings and conclusions, which are pertinent to our topic will be explored further in our subsequent discussions.

The first article by Htut, Shahrul and Poi (2007) was based on a qualitative study done to elicit the '*Views of Older Malaysians on Advanced Directives and Advanced Care Planning*'³⁵ while the second article by Jahn Kassim and Alias (2015b) explored

³⁴ *Syariah* is the most commonly used spelling in Malaysia, as compared to Syaria or Shari'a.

³⁵ See Appendix E for a summary of findings from this study.

*'Adequacies of ethical codes and developing legal standards on end-of-life decisions in Malaysia'*³⁶.

The following subsections explore some of the medical, legal, ethical and social aspects of end-of-life care in Malaysia in order to help our subsequent evaluation of implementing AdvDecs in this setting.

4.2 Medical

In Malaysia, medical professionals have always been seen as altruistic and moral in their activities³⁷ (Jahn Kassim and Jahn Kassim, 2014). The Malaysian healthcare system is generally divided between public healthcare facilities run by the government (public sector) and facilities that are privately owned (private sector).

Through the Malaysian Ministry of Health (MoH), the public sector facilities comprise of 139 public hospitals ranging from a 2229-bedded National Referral Hospital, to Tertiary Referral Hospitals in each of the country's 13 states and federal territories, several specialised hospitals such as the National Cancer Institute and the National Rehabilitation Hospital, and numerous rural district hospitals³⁸ (Ministry of Health, 2016). In addition to this, the MoH also runs 2836 health clinics, 195 *1Malaysia*

³⁶ Unfortunately, interest in end-of-life issues in Malaysia is a niche area of study, and thus, only very few authors have currently published relevant material on it. Among them are Professor Philip Poi, a Consultant Geriatrician; Dr. Richard Lim, a Consultant Palliative Care Physician; Professor Norchaya Talib and Professor Puteri Nemie Jahn Kassim, both Professors of Law.

³⁷ In recent years however, the medical profession has been subjected to criticism by society and has been accused of developing a tendency to protect their own interests at the expense of the public they serve. Commercialisation and globalisation have changed the social position of the doctor and the traditional values of society. The "automatic presumption of beneficence" has been dented by a number of civil malpractice and criminal cases (Jahn Kassim and Jahn Kassim, 2014, p.142).

³⁸ While at least one hospital is located in each district in Malaysia, most of these *district hospitals* only provide basic medical emergency and some inpatient services, but not resident specialist services.

clinics³⁹ and a Flying Doctor Service (FDS) to reach the interior and inaccessible areas in Borneo and Peninsula Malaysia. This MoH network is also supported by some Army Hospitals run by the Ministry of Defence (MinDef), and various University Teaching Hospitals run by the Ministry of Higher Education (MoHE). The fees charged for both outpatient and inpatient care at these public facilities are heavily subsidised by the government for its citizens while foreigners have to pay the full cost of receiving treatment.

On the other hand, the private sector consists of numerous hospitals, clinics and pharmacies that are mostly centred in the cities⁴⁰. Some of these facilities belong to healthcare conglomerates and have branches throughout the country, while others are set-up by individual practitioners. Some of these private centres boast of providing the latest technology and procedures in medicine and are marketed as medical tourism destinations with patients, irrespective of citizenship, being charged the full cost of treatment⁴¹.

Different practices between the public and private sector and within each sector will influence the implementation of AdvDecs. First and most importantly is the variation in the methods used to record patient notes. Much of the infrastructure of the public sector has been in use for a long time, and upgrading works have mainly been

³⁹ These clinics, are staffed by Medical Assistants, who are the equivalent of Physician Associates in the UK, and only provide basic medical and nursing care, such as first-aid, wound dressing, etc.

⁴⁰ A lucrative market for private healthcare services in Malaysia has led to the exponential increase in private healthcare facilities. In 1980, there were only 50 private hospitals with 1,171 beds but this increased to 9,949 beds in 224 hospitals in 2001, and by 2006, there were 11,637 private hospital beds (Jahn Kassim and Jahn Kassim, 2014).

⁴¹ Patients have the option of paying the cost for treatment themselves (termed 'self-paying patients') or through paying for private healthcare insurance (termed 'insurance-paying patients').

concentrated on improving physical facilities and manpower. As a result, patient notes are still handwritten in many of these public facilities with only a few of the newly built hospitals equipped with an electronic Total Hospital Information System (THIS). This is also because factors that need to be considered when implementing such a system include not only the budget for purchasing licensing software and hardware, but also the cost of maintaining them (which also includes considerations of methods to ensure confidentiality of patient data and the costs to maintain them). Even in hospitals where THIS has been implemented, a centralised electronic system to synchronise patient data and information between these hospitals is lacking and can be problematic when attempting to access decisions previously made about a patient's end-of-life care, especially when patients are referred for step-up or step-down care at other hospitals within the MoH network.

On the other hand, while most facilities in the private sector are equipped with electronic patient data systems such as THIS, these networks are also not linked to each other and patient data is confined only to the system of the particular institution.

Another important difference involves the big divide that exists in employment policies of healthcare staff, including doctors, between the public and private sector in Malaysia. Doctors in the public sector are first and foremost considered to be civil servants who are employed on a full-time and permanent basis. As such, generally speaking a doctor may only maintain a full-time practice in the private sector if they resign from government service, and when they do so, they should have completed their specialty or subspecialty training. Although measures are currently being taken

to evaluate the possibility of a public-private mix, this has still resulted in a lack of communication between both sectors in terms of referral for patient care.

Staffing issues also contribute to the lack of communication between the public and private sector. The constant reallocation of staff in the public sector⁴² frequently frustrate attempts by the private practitioner to identify the physician to contact regarding care of a patient who has been referred. This issue also happens within the public sector as the current practice in most hospitals do not implement a 'team' approach and patient care is still largely managed by anyone in the department who is assigned to that duty on the day (and this is liable to change on a daily basis).

In addition, the lack of training of healthcare staff especially doctors in discussing end-of-life issues will hinder efforts in implementing AdvDecs in Malaysia. An issue that is often debated has to do with identifying the best person to discuss AdvDecs with the patient. Should this be the consultant-in-charge, or should this task be delegated to someone more junior like the intern? If the answer is the latter, then should all doctors be trained and does formal training necessarily need to be undertaken in order to discuss these matters? Would it be possible for other healthcare staff besides doctors to discuss these issues with the patient and document them?

Another consideration is if this discussion necessarily needs to be conducted in a healthcare setting or would a similar discussion with a legal practitioner or even just

⁴² As with all civil servants, a doctor working in the public sector can be transferred to any healthcare facility within the MoH at any time, be it for training purposes or to meet the staffing demands of the particular facility.

an ordinary family member suffice? If the former is true, then another factor to consider is if there should be designated doctors who would be considered qualified to discuss these AdvDecs, and what their availability would be like, not only geographically, but also in terms of the timing of when this service will be provided.

Access to healthcare in Malaysia is also unique because on the one hand, a proper patient referral protocol⁴³ exists in the public sector whereas in the private sector, a patient can directly make an appointment to consult any doctor he or she wishes to. This has resulted in patients with an ischaemic stroke being cared for by neurologists, neurosurgeons, as well as general physicians, and patients who complain of epigastric pain presenting to surgeons who subsequently diagnose this to be a heart attack.

Accessibility to the services offered in both the public and private sectors also vary geographically and patients are not required to be registered with a designated General Practitioner (GP) in order to access primary healthcare. GP referrals are rare in the private setting and receiving a reply to the referral is even rarer. As such, it is easy to imagine how AdvDecs made may be lost in transition between referrals or how these may not be made known to the hospital doctor if they have been made in the GP setting and vice-versa.

While it is acknowledged that investigation results and X-rays contain data belonging to the patient, hardcopies of reports and X-rays films are considered to be public goods in the public sector as the government has paid for the cost of these items and

⁴³ Patients need to first visit a primary healthcare practitioner in the health clinic, or present themselves to the emergency department of the nearest hospital, before a subsequent referral to the relevant specialist is made if it is deemed necessary.

not the patient, while the contrary is true in the private sector where reports and films are given to the patients to be kept as they have been paid for by the patient. This complicates patient referrals from both the public to the private sector and the private to the public sector.

A further example of the public-private divide is highlighted by the different models used to operate palliative care services in Malaysia even though both the public and private sectors currently provide home-care and inpatient palliative care services (Leong, 2003).

Lastly, a strong belief in traditional medicine and remedies among Malaysian patients, who do not see these as a *complement* to Western medicine but rather as an *alternative*, can be a problem when discussing AdvDecs with patients. Very often, patients at the end-of-life wish to access these forms of alternative treatments even in the face of futility despite having chosen a more conservative approach to Western medicine. In addition, traditional healers and practitioners of alternative medicine do not seem to be held with the same amount of accountability and liability should any adverse events happen to the patient.

4.3 Legal

No legislation currently exists to provide guidance or enforce medical decisions made regarding end-of-life care in Malaysia (see also p.24). To recap the situation, the Medical Act (Malaysia) 1971 is the main legislation that governs medical practice in Malaysia while the Medical Regulations (Malaysia) 1974 governs the way the MMC functions. Both the Act and the Regulation fall under the purview of the MoH and

while there have been amendments made to both in 2012 and 2015 respectively, these changes have yet to be implemented. We have also explored a small part of the Mental Health Act (Malaysia) 2001 that relates to decision-making in instances of incapacity due to mental disorders (see also p.26).

While there appears to be some interest by non-governmental organisations (NGO) in advancing the cause of legislating the use of AdvDecs under some sort of regulation, specific information as to how this will be accomplished could not be obtained because these discussions and plans are still in their infancy and the findings have yet to be made public. As of 2015, Jahn Kassim and Alias (2015b) report that there have yet to be any cases regarding medical care at the end-of-life that have been brought to the Malaysian courts for resolution as they have traditionally been considered to be purely medical decisions.

It can therefore be said that the legal and ethical positions on these decisions can only be determined currently through evaluation of certain ethical codes and statutory decisions. Among these are the Malaysian guidelines on the *Code of Medical Ethics* (Malaysian Medical Association, 2001), the *Code of Professional Conduct* (Malaysian Medical Council, 1986) and the *Code of Professional Conduct for Nurses* (Nursing Board Malaysia, 1998). Although these guidelines do not have the force of law, all healthcare professionals who practice in the country are bound to abide by the guidelines issued in order to obtain their renewable licenses to practice.

With regards to medical decision-making by a competent adult patient, it is clear that the guiding principle in Malaysia is currently that of *respect for autonomy*. The standard is however less clear for those without the capacity to consent.

In the case of minors, parents or guardians of infants are given powers to make decisions for those under their care under Section 3 of the Guardianship of Infants Act (Malaysia) 1961 which stipulates that the guardian of an infant shall be responsible for his “support, health and education”. However, while there is no specific mention about what these constitute, Kaur (2011) suggests that these will include decisions made regarding healthcare matters, including those at the end-of-life.

On the other hand, determining who should be allowed to make healthcare decisions for mentally incapacitated adults is not as straightforward. According to Kaur (2011), the Mental Disorders Ordinance 1952 only provided for the care, reception and detention of persons of unsound mind in mental hospitals and is silent on matters relating to proxy decision-making. However this Ordinance, together with the Mental Health Ordinance (Sarawak) 1961 and the Lunatics Ordinance (Sabah) 1951 have since been repealed and replaced with the MHA(Malaysia) 2001.

While the provision in the old Ordinance regarding the courts’ power to appoint a committee and estate of a person following a determination that such a person is mentally disordered has been retained in Section 58 of the new MHA(Malaysia) 2001, Section 77 now provides guidance on how consent can be sought for care of patients without capacity, but these are only specific to consent for surgery, electro-convulsive therapy or clinical trials. It also mentions that consent is not required for other forms

of conventional therapy. However, the MHA(Malaysia) 2001 is mainly concerned with patients with psychiatric illnesses, and the answer to whether it would also cover patients who have lost the capacity to consent due to various other reasons such as a stroke or dementia remains vague in contrast to the MCA(UK) 2005. This also provides another strong reason for the implementation of AdvDecs in Malaysia.

The 2016 MMC guidelines *Consent For Treatment of Patients by Registered Medical Practitioners* in Section 18 provide for the existence of 'Advance Care Directives (ACD)' or LWs. It further divides care that is given into either emergency and non-emergency treatment and advises medical practitioners to provide treatment for the patient in accordance with their professional judgment of the patient's best interests in the emergency setting "until legal advice can be obtained on the validity or ambit of any Advance Care Directive that may have been given by the patient" (Malaysian Medical Council, 2016, s.18). If doubt regarding treatment arises in a non-emergency setting, consultation with the patient's spouse or next-of-kin should take place (*ibid.*).

The provisions in these guidelines are worrying on three accounts. The first reaffirms our prior discussion about the difficulty in establishing the validity of an ACD. It presumes that advanced directives exist and are made available, or attention of their existence and therefore their contents are made available to the treating doctors at the time the patient seeks treatment, including in an emergency situation. This of course does not happen in everyday practice. The second, and more worrying fact is that even if an ACD exists, it may be disregarded in both an emergency and non-emergency setting even though the guidelines do suggest that "a medical practitioner *should* refrain from providing treatment or performing any procedure where there is

an unequivocal written directive by the patient that such treatment or procedure is not to be provided in the circumstances which now apply to the patient” (*ibid.*, my italics). Thirdly, the provision for the ACD will only be considered if it is in the written form, and no mention is made regarding verbal requests which may be more common in the Malaysian setting.

The rare existence of AdvDecs in the Malaysian setting may also cause confusion among healthcare professionals and may eventually lead to queries about their validity and legality. This is made worse by an increasing rate of medical litigation in the country. Are these decisions legally binding? If they are not, should they be adhered to? If they are adhered to, should they be adhered to in their entirety? Can the patient’s family members still charge the doctor for negligence if the doctor adheres to a patient’s AdvDec with which they disagree?

In addition to all this, the provisions here all presuppose that patients are presented to hospitals for care. No mention is made of care in a non-hospital setting, be it in a care home or a hospice. This becomes important as the number of elderly people in the population is constantly increasing, as are the numbers of care homes.

We had earlier also alluded to a specific provision in the AMDA(Singapore) 1997 that makes it an offence to enquire whether an AMD has been made by a patient (see also p.24). The purpose of the inclusion of this provision by the Singaporean lawmakers is significant and it needs to be examined if a similar piece of legislation is to be drafted in the Malaysian setting. According to Lee (2016), this is to prevent coercion from

interested parties, and to ensure that patients who wished to make an AMD were free to do so voluntarily and without inducement or compulsion.

According to Talib (2002), *voluntary* passive euthanasia⁴⁴, which basically amounts to refusal of treatment that might lead to death is non-problematic in the Malaysian context and that the dilemma is more focused on *non-voluntary* passive euthanasia as physicians are generally more reluctant to withdraw treatment from patients for fear that its context may be misunderstood by the patient's relatives and lead to litigation.

Unfortunately, not many people think about their eventual demise and most patients will lack the capacity when the time arrives to make these decisions. Talib (2002) claims that two of the main reasons for refusal of treatment by patients in Malaysia are due to their wishes to go home or due to their family's wishes to seek treatment elsewhere⁴⁵, and therefore considers any withdrawal or withholding of treatment unrelated to passive euthanasia.

The impact of globalisation and the rate of migration as well as the efforts to promote Malaysia as a destination for medical tourism may shed some light on practical questions regarding AdvDecs that may not be answered with certainty due to the absence of any legislation in Malaysia. How will AdvDecs made in other countries, both by foreign patients who come to Malaysia for treatment and by Malaysians who have been residing in places where provisions for these are in place (for example in

⁴⁴ Passive euthanasia in Malaysia can be defined as "the act (or inaction) in bringing on death through non-intervention that includes both withholding and withdrawing treatment" (Talib, 2002, p.607).

⁴⁵ This could possibly be seeking treatment from another doctor in a different healthcare institution or an alternative medicine practitioner.

Singapore) affect their care when they are in a Malaysian setting? Are these AdvDecs applicable, or are the patients required to make a new one in Malaysia?

Lastly, a couple of points that need to be considered for any future legislation on AdvDecs in Malaysia include the distinction between Federal and State laws as provided for by the Federal Constitution that allows for special provisions applicable only to the two states of Sabah and Sarawak on a number of matters, and also the fact that the Federal Constitution provides for a unique dual-justice system that jointly administer Malaysian law although their respective jurisdictions remain separate. These significant points need to be considered as the *Syariah* courts have jurisdiction over matters including inheritance and marriages and divorce, while the influence of local customs, especially in Sabah and Sarawak, may come under the purview of the respective state legislatures. These considerations will also be alluded to in our subsequent discussion on social issues (see p.45, 51, 54-55).

While it is quite clear that the government does not have any immediate plans to create a comprehensive piece of legislation on AdvDecs for end-of-life decision-making, our discussion has emphasised the complexity and uniqueness of the case in Malaysia and there may likely be many obstacles or hurdles to be passed through before any legislation can be drafted. In the meantime, it appears that the current best practice would be to adhere to the guidelines provided by the MMC (2016) by virtue of the powers it has that have been extended from the Medical Regulations (Malaysia) 1974.

4.4 Ethical

Bioethics needs to be contextualised to local cultures and circumstances in order to be relevant (Campbell, 1999). In my paper *Beyond a Western Bioethics in Asia and its Implications on Autonomy* (Tan, 2016a, p.8), I discussed how the concept of autonomy in Asian culture does not only belong to the individual patient and how individuals are regarded as “a smaller self within a larger self” resulting in some situations where familial autonomy supersedes individual autonomy. As such, we need to recognise that decision-making, especially regarding issues of life and death, in a religion-oriented society like Malaysia where strong family and community support exist is often based on a consensus that is reached after extensive consultation with family members and trusted friends. This brings us to consider the following points when evaluating how AdvDecs can be implemented.

Firstly, let us look at the principles that will dominate the considerations of Malaysian society to either accept or reject the use of AdvDecs. While Jahn Kassim and Alias (2015a) propose in a paper that modern medical advances in the past century and the influences of Western medical practices have shifted the patient-doctor relationship and led to patient autonomy taking precedence over the principle of the sanctity of life, they however state in another that “decisions to prolong or discontinue life-supporting treatment directly impact upon the concept of sanctity of life, which forms the most fundamental principle of bioethics [in Malaysia]” (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015b, p.934). More significant though is the finding reported by Htut, Shahrul and Poi (2007) in their qualitative study that the majority of Malaysians consider

themselves to be religious⁴⁶. Considering that the majority of the population in Malaysia are Muslims, the prevailing principle would most likely to be one that is consistent with Islamic teaching- that of the *sanctity of life* that has been given by God and that only He can decide when to take it back (Alibhai, 2008).

Having established that the sanctity of life principle is likely to take precedence over autonomy in Malaysian society, our second point to consider is the relationship between individual autonomy and familial autonomy. Three situations within the scenario of autonomy and end-of-life care decision-making that need to be considered individually are described here.

4.4.1 Autonomy and breaking bad news

In the Malaysian setting, as in other Asian cultures, it would seem acceptable for physicians to discuss a patient's diagnosis with his or her next-of-kin first, especially where the patient is an elderly one. There is evidence to show that patients are generally accepting and sometimes even happier with this arrangement (Htut, Shahrul and Poi, 2007). Some possible arguments for this practice include the possibility of family members viewing their responsibility to include sheltering the sick patient from stressful information and difficult choices, but also a possible beneficent intent on the physician's part to spare the elderly patient the anguish of receiving the bad news or allowing someone more familiar to break it to the patient (Lee, 2014). While this model of practice may work in some situations, it will certainly create problems for establishing AdvDecs when a decision or request is

⁴⁶ At least 50% of the respondents, of which the majority was Muslim, admitted to being strongly religious.

made by family members to withhold the diagnosis or information about treatment options from the patient.

4.4.2 Autonomy and consent

Our earlier discussions have presupposed that patients who utilise AdvDecs have the capacity to make decisions, are able to consider the pros and cons of the information provided, and that the informed consent that they provide is free from coercion. However, in the Malaysian context, the possibility that the final decisions are sometimes not made by the patient but by the head of their family or some other relative exists. The cases of *Gurmit Kaur Jaswant Singh v Tung Shin Hospital & Anor* (2013) and *Abdul Razak bin Datuk Abu Samah v Raja Badrul Hisham Raja Zezeman Shah & Ors* (2013) provide guidance on consent to medical treatment in the Malaysian setting. Both these judgements seem to suggest that consenting to treatment in some cases require *familial* or *spousal* intervention. If this is the case for gynaecological procedures and also where a female patient is regarded to be dependant on her husband, then how much more when it comes to consenting to decisions regarding end-of-life care. While this custom may be true for Muslims, where a Muslim wife may need to submit to the decision of her husband, the fact that needs to be acknowledged is that different ethnicities and religions do also prescribe different rituals and customs that will impact the way consent is given for AdvDecs. A further point to note here is that there is currently no guidance in the Malaysian courts with regards to when the patient is the husband rather than the wife.

4.4.3 Autonomy and best interests

The role of the family in decision-making in Asia is strikingly different from that of the West. This is most evident when considering the relationship between autonomy and best interests based on the question “whose best interests take precedence, and who determines this” (Tan, 2016a, p.13). Arguably, there may be instances when the best interests of the family supersede that of the individual. In addition to that, the patient’s understanding of what his or her best interests are may differ from what their family members think. While this may not pose much of a problem when the family is in a harmonious state, the situation becomes more complicated when family disputes occur between family members.

Although the younger generation of Malaysians may be more influenced by Western thought, a strong sense of filial piety still remains. Children and parents may have a mismatch of perceptions when it comes to decisions on end-of-life care and some children may not be able to accept the choices their parents have made, leading to a complicated situation when patients subsequently lack capacity as their prior decisions may not be legally binding. A further point that can be raised is that while all parents love their children, not all children love their parents. When disputes occur due to ulterior motives rather than best interests, referring to written legislations would probably be the most effective means of dispute resolution.

Some of the ethical considerations with regards to implementing AdvDecs stem from issues regarding beneficence and non-maleficence. One of the principles most often

quoted by healthcare professionals is *primum non nocere*⁴⁷. According to Jahn Kassim and Alias (2015b, p.937) “many ethicists contend that doctors have a moral obligation that may outweigh their duty to respect a patient's wishes, particularly where end-of-life decisions are concerned” and “a doctor's obligation to his or her patient extends beyond the prevention of harm, and includes restoration and improvement of the quality of life”. Not only are these statements in accordance to the *primum non nocere* principle, they are also in agreement with our earlier discussion on the primacy of the sanctity of life principle over autonomy in the Malaysian setting.

Jahn Kassim and Alias (2015b, p.936) also argue that “patients' preferences are not decisive unless a beneficial medical perspective is present” and that “doctors are not obliged to honor requests for interventions that confer no medical benefit to the patient or treatments that would expose the patient to more harm than good, as this would constitute a direct violation of the values of the medical profession and show disrespect towards the concept of patient autonomy”.

While doctors may like to think that paternalism could still hold some weight in decision-making at the end-of-life, there is no denying that healthcare economics also play an important role here. We have already discussed the difficulties faced between the public and private sectors and have seen that there is a lack of communication between both sectors, and that the facilities may differ due to different priorities⁴⁸

⁴⁷ This is translated into English as ‘first do no harm’.

⁴⁸ The public sector being more concerned with providing basic essential care to the masses, while the private sector focuses on investing in medical tourism and the availability of the latest advances in medical technology in order to maximise profit.

(see also p.32-36). At the end of the day, whenever medicine is run as a business for profit, the increased cost will deny good medical care to the poor. Self-paying and insurance-paying patients will also have different expectations of treatment outcomes and will be more willing to challenge doctors and hospitals if these expectations are not met (Jahn Kassim and Jahn Kassim, 2014). Therefore, another issue that has the potential to influence decisions on AdvDecs, particularly in the private sector, is the influence of insurance⁴⁹.

What kinds of treatment will insurance companies pay for? In Malaysia, insurance companies offer both medical and life insurances. While the majority of the elderly population do not possess any insurance policies and rely on the public sector, especially in the rural parts of the country, an increasing amount of patients are purchasing insurance in order to be able to afford private health care services. In the USA, insurance companies are gradually moving away from paying for treatment at the end-of-life and are leaning towards encouraging the use of palliative care services. There have also been reports that these insurance companies will now pay for physician-assisted suicide (PAS) or euthanasia⁵⁰. While these options are currently not legal or available in Malaysia, the more likely scenario will involve the limit to which insurance companies will pay for certain types of treatment when faced between a choice of expensive treatment (e.g. chemotherapy and renal dialysis)

⁴⁹ This refers to both medical healthcare insurance for patients and medical indemnity insurance for healthcare professionals. Both of these types of insurances will increase the cost of private healthcare services.

⁵⁰ One such case involved a 64-year-old Oregon woman named Barbara Wagner who was diagnosed with recurrent lung cancer and required chemotherapy. Her insurance company refused to pay for the drugs because it did not meet their 5% survival rate after 5 years policy but would cover her palliative care treatment or drugs for a physician-assisted suicide (James, 2008)

versus palliative care. The ability to access funding for treatment will definitely influence decisions regarding AdvDecs.

4.5 Social

“Decisions are no longer confined to clinical assessments; rather, they involve wider considerations such as a patient's religious and cultural beliefs, financial constraints, and the wishes and needs of family members. These decisions affect everyone concerned, including members of the community as a whole. Therefore it is imperative that clear ethical codes and legal standards are developed to help guide the medical profession on the best possible course of action for patients” (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2016, p.934)

Decision-making in end-of-life care is often a delicate and sensitive process, as the clinical evaluation of a patient does not only involve his or her physical prognosis, but considerations about the patient's emotional wellbeing as well as their personal beliefs, values and customs which may be influenced by their religion and level of spirituality need to be taken into account. These discussions are becoming increasingly difficult due to the existence of a global phenomenon of hiding and denying death rather than facing it (see also p.2). People nowadays do not die in the way they used to and whilst a vast majority of patients still express the desire to be in their own homes, surrounded by their loved ones, when the momentous event of death occurs, this does not happen that often in reality (Nuland, 1995). An increasing number of people are dying in healthcare facilities, therefore making AdvDecs an important and possibly a necessary part of the standard care provided for the dying (Gawande, 2016b).

We have already discovered how the lack of AdvDecs legislation in Malaysia can be problematic (see also p.37-40). This has resulted in suggestions by some Malaysian lawyers that the best way to overcome the lack of discussion on end-of-life issues in Malaysia would be by implementing professional codes of conduct that govern medical practice as it will guide doctors on how to perform their duties (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015b). The argument for this is that comprehensive enforcement of such guidelines would be attainable when affirmed and backed by the law and will serve to regulate end-of-life decisions and provide clear guidance to doctors to ensure that their actions do not culminate in unwanted legal repercussions.

However, before we agree to these claims, we need a deeper discussion on what kind of social impact this will create. While we may be able to postulate many of these social impacts in different ways, they can mainly be seen from the perspectives of culture and religion.

4.5.1 Culture

As mentioned, Malaysia comprises of a multi-ethnic society. While each ethnic group will have their own traditions and cultural observances, there are also some significant practices that have been acculturated and adopted to try to build a national identity that is based on the commonalities rather than the differences between races and religions. Translated to everyday medical practice, this means that while the healthcare professional has to be sensitive to the requirements of each individual patient, there are certain accepted practices in Malaysia that may appear to be alien to the traditional or Western view of medical ethics and professionalism.

Starting with a more universal trait, it appears that many Malaysian patients, just like those from many other societies, have never considered and much less communicated their wishes for treatment at the end-of-life. This sometimes results in decisions that are taken by the medical team being in conflict with the values of the patient or the requests of the family. Many patients in Malaysia, especially those of the older generation still have a rather fatalistic view of life, perceiving their condition as being *God's will* (Htut, Shahrul and Poi, 2007).

In analysing this situation, there are three contributing factors that can be identified. Firstly, the influence of religion appears to play a significant role in developing this way of life. Muslims believe that they must not end their lives through any intervention as it implies a lack of trust in Allah and His plan (Tan, 2016b, p.10). At the same time, they also trust that there is no sickness that is too difficult for Allah to cure, and that for every problem that has been created by Allah, He has also created a solution for it (Daar and Al Khitamy, 2001). Other religions on the other hand also teach about the sanctity of life and the meaning of suffering. It appears that a theistic belief of religion provides hope and meaning for these patients. The role of religion can also be seen when choosing treatment options, and this again will influence choices within a Malaysian version of AdvDecs. Medications that are manufactured with impure or prohibited substances such as the porcine-based material in Clexane become a major consideration for some patients (Padela, 2013).

This leads us to the second point about trust: different patients have different levels and concepts of trust. We have already seen how the role of religion and trust in God are important considerations for Malaysian patients. In some parts of the country,

there still exists a very strong level of trust in the patient-doctor relationship. This is also strengthened in the private setting by the ability to self-refer or to visit the patient's doctor of choice. From my experience, 'doctor, you decide' or 'do whatever you think is best' are not uncommon replies from patients after sitting through an extensive consultation exploring treatment options and explaining the risks and benefits of each option. This may also possibly be the reason that medical practice in Malaysia still retains some element of paternalism. A further relationship of trust exists between patients and their families and this can be seen from some of the conclusions observed in Htut, Shahrul and Poi's (2007) research. In deciding on care at the end-of-life, a majority of Malaysians feel that they would like their children or a proxy to make those decisions for them. Although this appears to be increasingly alien in the Western world, it is still quite common in the Asian culture. Talib (2002, p.610) describes how when the prognosis of the patient is thought to be poor, or an imminent cardiac arrest is foreseen, the medical team will usually consult the relatives of the patient as to whether any active resuscitation should be carried out and the wishes of the relatives would be acceded to, therefore making the decision taken not solely that of the healthcare team.

Our third point is with regards to a possible lack of knowledge in the general population. Doctors have traditionally been held to possess a knowledgeable and trusted position in the Malaysian society. This, and the fact that new medical technologies nowadays provide many treatment options for a single condition, results in many patients feeling overwhelmed when needing to make such a decision. The level of education of the older population is also not very high considering that Malaysia only achieved its independence in 1957 and remains a developing nation.

Many of these patients, especially those living in the more rural areas of the country, lead simple lives and are not used to making life or death decisions, or planning for these kinds of situations. Death is still accepted as a fact of life, and many of these patients feel uncomfortable even with the mere thought of being brought to hospital for treatment. In contrast, to the city-dwellers and the younger generation, talking about death appears to be a topic that is taboo. As a result of these factors, formally written AdvDecs may not be utilised by the older patients and the younger ones may not accept its implementation.

A further consideration in our discussion on the influence of culture on the use of AdvDecs is found in the argument that while it is universally acknowledged that competent patients are allowed to make autonomous decisions even if those decisions will result in death, this is not much of an issue in Malaysia (Talib, 2005). It is interesting to note that Talib bases this claim on the fact that a patient's refusal of treatment is almost always due to patients or their family members wanting to seek treatment elsewhere⁵¹ and not because the patient wants to die. Admittedly, traditional medicine still maintains a huge influence in Malaysia, especially among the less educated, the elder generation and those living in more rural areas. It is so popular that the MoH has set up a division that is in charge of regulating the use of traditional and complementary medicine (TCM). Invariably, most TCM practitioners are not held liable and are not required to maintain the same level of accountability as healthcare professionals practising Western medicine. As such, it remains to be seen how TCM can be included as an option in AdvDecs.

⁵¹ Again, this could be seeking a second or even third opinion, or to seek treatment from a traditional healer.

A criticism of Talib's reasoning is that patients in Malaysia do not always refuse treatment for the reasons she mentions. The values and the things that are important to patients in Malaysia differ from the West, and many will take into consideration the welfare of their spouses or children or their current life situation in order to make decisions whether to accept a proposed treatment or not (see also p.45). It appears absurd for a patient to travel 200km for chemotherapy 2-3 times a week if they reside in the rural areas, and it would definitely not make sense to a single elderly patient with end-stage renal disease to travel to the city for a fistula operation, and then be asked to undergo dialysis for 3 times a week.

Similarly, Jahn Kassim and Alias (2016) state that end-of-life care from a healthcare perspective is a specific component of palliative care. Unfortunately, this is not entirely true in the Malaysian setting as the MoH in fact aims for all its healthcare workers to be able to provide basic palliative care to patients at the end-of-life. This is primarily due to the lack of established dedicated palliative care centres in the rural areas despite this branch of medicine being introduced in 1991, but also due to the difficulty that many patients will face in travelling long distances to avail of this care if doctors who work in the outskirts and rural setting are not able to provide this service.

A final point to note in this section is the claim by Talib (2005) when considering the dilemma surrounding passive euthanasia in Malaysia that results from the physician's uncertainty of the meaning and implication of the term. This is often caused by the

misguided perceptions of relatives and lay people⁵² and is another reason why patients in Malaysia would be hesitant to make a written AdvDec.

4.5.2 Religion

A patient's religious affiliation is an important factor in medical decision-making, and it even sometimes plays an intervening role in end-of-life decision-making. As we have already seen, Islam plays a dominant role in the Malay culture (see also p.43). In Malaysia, it is mandatory for all Malays to be Muslim, and it is also mandatory for anyone of another ethnicity or religion who marries a Muslim to convert to Islam. We have also previously mentioned the role of the *Syariah* Court. Islamic bioethics works within a framework of values derived from revelation and tradition that is linked directly to *Syariah* law and Muslims in Malaysia commonly seek *fatawa* (legal rulings, singular *fatwa*) by Islamic jurists in order to determine what they can or cannot do (Bakar, 1986).

In Western culture, it may be common for patients with a terminal illness to consider a premature death. This is evident from the use of euthanasia in countries like the Netherlands, Belgium, Switzerland, and more recently Canada as well as PAS in some American states. There have also been recent discussions regarding moving away from the use of medical assistance in dying (MAID) to voluntarily stopping eating and drinking (VSED) (Pope and Hexum, 2012). While these requests can provide an opportunity for physicians to explore with patients their fears and wishes, and also to

⁵² For example, that disconnecting a life-support machine from a brain-dead patient is equivalent to passive euthanasia.

enlighten them regarding other options available in the form of palliative care⁵³, these methods of incurring a premature death would certainly not be permitted by Islam or most of the other religions in Malaysia.

In Talib's view, death is culturally accepted as part of life in Malaysia even though it may not be talked about much (Talib, 2005). She also affirms that physicians are not expected to save lives at all costs. This originates from the view that death is not an end in and of itself, and allowing a patient to die is morally appropriate as "the belief is that the patient should not be hindered from continuing his journey of life into the next stage" (*ibid.*, p.611). It is because of this that the Islamic, Christian, Buddhist and Hindu authorities in Malaysia consider withdrawing and withholding futile treatment as permissible and this view will certainly influence AdvDecs in Malaysia.

A final point to consider is one raised in Htut, Shahrul and Poi's (2007) study that most patients prefer dying at home. This appears to be a universal trend (O'Mahony, 2016; Gawande, 2014), however the reason for this in their study interestingly enough was not because of the usual wish to be in a familiar surrounding and being among friends and family, but was mainly so that the prescribed religious rituals could be carried out.

⁵³ Studies have shown that often once the provider has addressed patients' concerns, they may choose not to pursue PAS (Steinbock, 2005.)

Chapter 5 Evaluating AdvDecs Use and Determining Best Practices

The actual end-of-life care that patients get is often different from what they desire. A good example is illustrated by the discrepancy between their place of preference for dying and where it actually takes place. While the majority of patients desire to die at home, most of them die in hospitals or other care homes (Nuland, 1995). An estimated 85% of people also believe that doctors should have end-of-life conversations with patients, but only 15% have ever conducted such a discussion (Gawande, 2016b, p.6). Similarly in Malaysia, 50% of respondents to a survey would consider making plans for future management but none of them had ever heard of ACP or its concept (Htut, Shahrul and Poi, 2007).

Nevertheless, our discussion has demonstrated how AdvDecs can provide assurance and reinforcement that a competent patient's right to make autonomous decisions will not be affected by any future incapacity⁵⁴. Asking patients about their preferences and needs and understanding them are the first steps towards respecting patient autonomy at the end-of-life (Gawande, 2016b).

Various studies have demonstrated that physicians usually react positively towards patients possessing AdvDecs, but this does not always translate into physicians adhering to them, and consequently sometimes results in more suffering for patients⁵⁵ (Coleman, 2012). Among the reasons that some jurisdictions permit physicians not to comply with patient preferences include that the patient's AdvDec

⁵⁴ This is because AdvDecs should be developed as a tool to enhance and satisfy patient autonomy.

⁵⁵ This could be due to the complexity of decision-making at the bedside or even possibly due to physicians not being comfortable initiating discussions about AdvDecs.

includes an act that is contrary to the law; that an AdvDec was written too long ago; that there have been significant advances in medical sciences that are relevant to the decision in question; or that there have been reasons to infer that the patient has changed their mind or if it could be inferred that a different decision would have been made had the patient had adequate knowledge of the current circumstances (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009). These usually arise as many physicians affiliate AdvDecs only with medical crises and thus many discussions occur when the patient may not be in the right frame of mind (Kubler-Ross, 1970, p.125; Gawande, 2016b).

In Malaysia, where no legislation currently exists on AdvDecs, many factors need to be evaluated before these suggestions can be implemented. Firstly, the *lack of published evidence* (see also p.30) from a Malaysian context does not portray an accurate account of the perception of Malaysian patients and doctors on this matter⁵⁶. What it does portray is *a lack of political will* by the government to promote research and education into this topic that subsequently results in *the lack of education* of the general public.

Secondly, medical schools currently *do not place enough emphasis* on ensuring medical students are proficient in communicating with patients at the end-of-life, nor do they inculcate their students with sufficient skills to facilitate decision-making regarding issues that may arise. This results in the *production of junior doctors who*

⁵⁶ Even the articles that do claim to provide a Malaysian context often cite Western sources. While this may add supporting evidence to an authors claim, this needs to be synthesised and interpreted for use in the Malaysian context. It must not fall into the trap of conflating the notion that suggests that everything quoted is applicable to the Malaysian setting.

are not confident and uncomfortable at initiating these kinds of discussions with patients.

Evidence has also revealed that patients classified as ‘Do Not Attempt Cardio-Pulmonary Resuscitation (DNACPR)’ receive reduced frequency of visits from their doctors because some doctors are ashamed to acknowledge the ‘failures’ of modern medicine⁵⁷ (O’Mahony, 2016). Additionally, Htut, Shahrul and Poi’s (2007) study also revealed some Malaysian patients who would welcome life-prolonging treatment despite there being no hope of recovery. What these two points imply is that one of the most important obstacle that needs to be considered when implementing AdvDecs is how we can *overcome the lack of knowledge and understanding* of the subject not only by patients on the receiving end of healthcare, but also by healthcare professionals who are involved in the provision of medical services because death is *not* always a failure (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a; Gawande, 2016b).

Thirdly, our discussion has highlighted how the *cultural and religious contexts of AdvDecs are not always clearly delineated*⁵⁸. This can create confusion when there is a mismatch of expectations or miscommunication between the parties involved. Assimilation and acculturation are important in determining the best approaches and

⁵⁷ O’Mahony (2016, p.136) accurately portrays this situation when he writes that “while this may sound absurd to some, it does reflect how doctors have been trained, and the attitudes junior doctors have learnt from their consultants. They do not realise that it is not just sympathy that the dying need, but also practical things like pain relief and relief from itching, nausea, breathlessness, terror”. This ‘failure’ is also acknowledge by Gawande (2016b) in his statement to the USA Senate Special Committee for Aging.

⁵⁸ Jahn Kassim and Alias (2016, p.122) write that “the extent that Islamic principles can be applied in this same area is uncertain, as specific provisions on the subject matter have yet to be incorporated in their respective laws or ethical codes.”

the practicality of issues such as the legal effect of AdvDecs and what their contents should be.

The values and spiritual beliefs of patients are extremely significant at the end-of-life as these provide a sense of security and belonging to them by offering a way to find meaning in dying as in life (Kubler-Ross, 1970). Some of these values and beliefs may compete with one another and result in inconsistencies in definitions and practices. This is possibly the reason why Talib (2005) argues that setting up guidelines and legislations would help to settle any existing uncertainty and confusion in Malaysia.

Jahn Kassim and Alias (2016) have also written regarding the importance of medical professionals being guided on issues such as ethical obligations, legal demands and religious expectations prior to handling difficult end-of-life decisions. Developing comprehensive ethical codes in congruence with developing legal standards have also been suggested as they may help to guide the medical profession in making sound medical decisions that are sensitive to the varying religious beliefs and cultural values of their patients (Tallon, 2012).

However, we need to note that legal intervention in itself may cause problems particularly when the courts find themselves acting as mediators in complex and frequently distressing clinical scenarios (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2016). This is further compounded by suggestions that the current prevailing medical ethics that have supplanted the Hippocratic ethics (especially regarding autonomy) is primarily a Western product and is thus incompatible with other cultures. Should the Malaysian

legal system then *prima facie* support the legality of AdvDecs or view them in merely an advisory role?

In another article, Jahn Kassim and Alias (2015a) also predict some of the limitations involved in legislating AdvDecs in Malaysia that includes stipulating the terms used in the contents of AdvDecs and the lack of relevant information. These usually result from:

- (1) Doctors not being skilled in facilitating discussions.
- (2) Doctors not providing adequate information to the patient.
- (3) Patients' inability to understand the options fully to make an autonomous and informed decision.

In attempting to find a solution to these problems, they argue that a detailed checklist would be too restrictive, but additional cost would be incurred if a lengthy consultation process were to occur. They have, more importantly though, compiled a pertinent list of requirements that need to be considered before AdvDecs are implemented in Malaysia (refer to Appendix F).

Others have also emphasised the need for strict provisions that ensure doctors or family members do not misuse AdvDecs for financial considerations⁵⁹ and that the AdvDecs can be located when the need arises (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009). However, O'Mahony (2016) does point out that AdvDecs having a weak legal status or lacking formal legislation, such as in some common-law countries, does not necessarily equate to a true impediment for good decision-making about care at the

⁵⁹ The motivation for this can be due to different considerations. For example, for the physician it may be the desire to reduce healthcare costs, while for the family members it may be how to support the patient financially, or be linked to the question of the amount of inheritance to be left.

end-of-life. This is because physicians will have a broader margin for discretion in their decision-making and judicial decisions already often recognise the right of the next-of-kin to make decisions with physicians where patients' wishes can be taken into account even if it is not memorialised in formal AdvDecs (O'Mahony, 2016, p.269).

What we have gathered so far is that medicine does not merely deal with elements of pure science, but also with intrinsic humanistic and ethical components (Steinberg, 2003). We have also discussed how moral recognition is sometimes independent of legal status, and that AdvDecs can be misused by doctors or family members to neglect some patients, and not give them the treatment they need (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009). Some view AdvDecs as excessively individualistic to the extent of disregarding the role of family members in decision-making while others recommend using a broader term, not limiting them to only patient's *wishes* only but also to include their *goals and values*. This leads us to ponder if there will be any significant difference whether AdvDecs become legally binding or not? What seems to matter most is that whatever decisions we make about the legality of AdvDecs, they need to be compatible with the socio-cultural differences that exist between ethnicities and religions in Malaysia.

The best recommendation currently would then take the form of a step-wise approach. The first step would be to *get people talking about their wishes and life values* irrespective of whether they are currently at an end-of-life situation or not. We know that by the time they reach the end of their lives, many people have multiple conditions and complex needs that require a proactive, coordinated response, and

therefore it would be apt to start these conversations early (NHS IQ, 2014a). A model similar to the Conversation Project (2016) can be utilised to approach this topic. In order to promote this culture of talking about death, support needs to be garnered from all stakeholders including the government, other NGOs and the people involved in both the public and private healthcare settings, as well as everyone involved in the legal and medical fraternities. Malaysians have many occasions to discuss this topic and we must latch on to this opportunity especially during the various cultural and religious holidays when families get together⁶⁰. Advertisements and promotion campaigns as well as seminars can be held to encourage people to discuss these issues when they meet during these festivals.

A second step that should take place simultaneously is to *improve the communication skills of all parties involved in end-of-life care*, especially those between patients and doctors, patients and their family members, family members and doctors, and also between private and public healthcare personnel. This can start with the introduction of curriculums in medical schools that encourages medical students to acquire cultural competence⁶¹ while also organising educational sessions and workshops for existing healthcare personnel on the importance of a framework that includes measures of religiousness and spirituality as these will enable them to better understand their patients' beliefs, values, expectations and needs and to assist them

⁶⁰ *Hari Raya Aidilfitri* (or better known as '*Eid*') is a celebration in Malaysia where Muslims return to their '*kampung*'s' (villages), and similarly the Chinese Lunar New Year and the Harvest Festival are celebrations when the Chinese and the various indigenous communities in Borneo gather with their families respectively.

⁶¹ Carey and Cosgrove (2006, p.264) describe this as "the acquisition of the knowledge and skills that enhance the management of cultural issues in the clinical environment [that] requires skilled verbal and non-verbal communication as a means of appreciating differences".

in facilitating a dynamic interaction between patients, family members and healthcare professionals (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2016).

In addition to this, we also realise that “in certain contexts, failure to perform an act, with foreseen bad consequences of that failure, is morally less bad than to perform a different act which has the identical foreseen consequences” (Glover, 1990, pp.92-3). Healthcare professionals are held to their professional ethics that view allowing the natural progression of an illness as opposed to making something happen by acting intentionally to be more acceptable legally and ethically (*ibid.*). The principle of *proportionality* should also be applied with regard to life-sustaining treatments in end-of-life care. Therefore, when communication levels are enhanced, doctors will be able to provide the optimal care for their patients without the fear of litigation⁶².

Once these two steps have been implemented, only then should the third step, which is to *legislate provisions for AdvDecs*, take place. When this eventually happens, there will be a need to be open to applying a flexible approach that provides multiple options of AdvDecs due to the uniqueness of the situation that the Malaysian society finds itself in. Public discussions and consultations should of course take place regarding the role that such legislation *could* and *should* play in clinical practice. Any subsequent legal standards concerning AdvDecs will also definitely need to take into account the values and perspectives of the different communities that make up Malaysia’s racial and religious demography (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2015a).

⁶² A majority of medico-legal litigation takes place due to a breakdown in communication.

In addition to this, the development of medical codes of ethics that can be affirmed as good practice and are compatible with current developments of the law will be essential (Jahn Kassim and Alias, 2016). For this to take place, the medical fraternity will need to decide which principles these codes will be based on, and how much emphasis will be placed on *personal autonomy* and *best interests of the patient*, and how to achieve the correct balance between those of familial or communal autonomy and the allocation of scarce medical and financial resources.

Lastly, the establishment of a hospital, state, regional or national database of AdvDecs should also be considered in any future legislation that will be promulgated, taking into account how these can be accessed by both doctors in the public and private healthcare setting. The question of whether or to what extent AdvDecs made in one country can be effectively followed in another country whose legislation does not give the same legal effect to such documents should also be considered if we are to take into account the large number of medical tourists who visit the South East Asian region (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009).

Chapter 6 Examining Impact of Implementing AdvDecs: Paving the Way Forward

Predicting the future is never easy because of the uncertainties involved but a vision is always needed in order to successfully complete a mission. The primary purpose of implementing or legislating AdvDecs in Malaysia should not be to respect autonomy but more for the consideration of how to determine the best interests of patients and their families. Very often, along with death, the dying patient's problems come to an end, but their family's problems go on (Kubler-Ross, 1970, p.142). The ultimate aim would be to provide an avenue where doctors can make *shared decisions* with their patients and family members that allows doctors to honour their professional integrity and moral obligations to their patients while ensuring patients and their families feel that due consideration has been given to their life values and wishes and consequently that their autonomy has been respected.

If these kind of *partnership decisions* can be achieved collectively through using different forms of AdvDecs, then the way forward in Malaysian healthcare will be able to grow healthily. With AdvDec legislations in place, the hope is that this will help more people talk about death and dying as an intrinsic part of life just as they do not hesitate to mention when someone is expecting a new baby. The topic will then become common enough that doctors do not need to ask themselves if they ought to bring this topic up with a patient or if they should wait until the last admission (*ibid.*, p.125).

The hope is also that patients and their family members will be ready when decisions have to be made about their care. If the AdvDecs are in a written form, patients will have a copy of them at all times, or maybe possess a card similar to those of organ donors in their wallet. The setting up of the centralised database or registry will enable hospitals and their staff to access information about the patients AdvDecs (either to access a copy of the written document, or to access information of who to call if a healthcare proxy has been selected)⁶³. What this presumes is that AdvDecs have been set up for everyone and its contents can be made available to the treating doctors.

According to O'Mahony (2016, p.267), legislation on AdvDecs have often resulted as a response to the pleas of judges for assistance in deciding a number of high-profile cases involving physicians' insistence on continuing life-support that patients' families found inappropriate. We also hope that clear guidelines and legislations will help to dispel this confusion, that families and patients and their healthcare providers will understand the interplay between religious and cultural viewpoints with actual medical practice. This will also determine the exact situations when doctors have a moral obligation that may outweigh their duty to respect a patient's wishes (Jahn Kassim, Alias and Muhammad, 2014).

In order to achieve this utopian medical dream, the three steps described need to be thoroughly and systematically implemented. Education and communication are both key to its success. These will be implemented through the inclusion of the topic on

⁶³ Something similar to the National Registry of Advance Directives in Spain and Singapore that is coordinated through the implementation of a web-based network. (Andorno, Biller-Andorno and Brauer, 2009)

AdvDecs into medical school curriculum and regular workshops for existing healthcare professionals as well as campaigns broadcast on radio, television and the social media.

Special clinics will need to be set up for trained clinicians, or some clinic hours in a GP setting can be set aside, to allow patients to discuss AdvDecs or to make a statement of their wishes or simply for patients and their family members to get more information or clarification about their options and choices. To this end, it is also worth mentioning the possible use of certified Patient Decision Aids (PDA) similar to those that will be implemented in the USA in 2018 for end-of-life aids⁶⁴.

Lastly, based on studies of patient preferences at the end-of-life, it can be envisioned that if AdvDecs are well implemented, then there will be a *growth in demand for palliative care and hospice services* as patients come to grasp with the reality of their mortality (Gawande, 2016b). Unfortunately, while this issue needs to be addressed and assessed thoroughly in order for appropriate responses to be made in terms of the provision of facilities, exploring and answering this question goes beyond the scope of this dissertation.

⁶⁴ According to Pope and Hexum (2013), PDAs are evidenced-based educational tools that are accurate, complete, and understandable. While more than 130 randomised controlled trials have shown that they are highly effective, they have not been used to their full capacity in clinical practice yet.

Chapter 7 Conclusion

Our discussion has brought us on a journey that started by first exploring the different forms of AdvDecs currently in place. We learnt how AdvDecs first started with the introduction of LWs, and how the quest to strike a balance between autonomy and paternalism in order to preserve a person's right to consent have brought forth improvements and innovations in the various forms of AdvDecs currently used, resulting in those that are written legal documents to those of the more informal oral forms.

The discussion then focused on considering some current relevant legislations in the form of the MCA(UK) 2005, the AMDA(Singapore) 1996 and the relevant ethical codes and legal provisions in Malaysia governing aspects of end-of-life decision-making. It also highlighted the lack of judicial decisions in this area and the limitations of the Malaysian regulatory system.

Before advocating for the development of comprehensive ethical codes and legal standards to guide end-of-life decision-making in Malaysia, we studied the major influencing factors that would determine the successful implementation of AdvDecs from the medical, legal, ethical and social points of view. We realised that a great divide exists between the public and private healthcare systems in Malaysia. Sensitivity towards cultural and religious differences of Malaysian society is also a prominent feature and the importance of healthcare providers inquiring into and evaluating their patient's religious and spiritual beliefs as well as their personal attitudes towards end-of-life issues such as illness, pain and death was emphasised.

In Islam, the saving of a life is considered one of the highest merits and doctors must do everything they can to prevent a premature death (Zahedi, Larijani and Bazzaz, 2007). We discovered that this however, does not come at all costs, and when death is inevitable or if treatment is futile, life-saving acts ceases to be mandatory⁶⁵ (Khan, Lazarus and Owens, 2002).

We then arrived at evaluating the use of AdvDecs and attempting to determine best practices in the Malaysian setting, questioning if it would be superfluous, useless or difficult to interpret and implement AdvDecs in such a multi-cultural and multi-religious society. Understanding the manifold ethical dilemmas involved, we proposed a structured approach considering the different value systems of each individual patient. Emphasis was placed on the importance of adequate and effective communication between all interested parties to minimise misunderstanding and conflict. In order to increase trust of a compassionate and improved end-of-life care environment, a mutual and collective shared decision-making approach was promoted.

In examining the impact of AdvDecs on Malaysian society, we envisioned an integrated approach to its promotion by the government and NGOs as well as the implementation of educational programmes for current and future healthcare

⁶⁵ Islam recognises that there are times in which human beings need to recognise their own limits and let nature take its course (Quran 39:42) and that resorting to futile treatment in order to put off death is not acceptable in Islam (Zahedi, Larijani and Bazzaz, 2007).

personnel. The establishment of an integrated registry was also explored, and the growth in the field of palliative care medicine was predicted⁶⁶.

We end this discussion with a quote from Jahn Kassim and Alias (2015a, p.20), that:

“in Malaysia, the need for advance directive legislation has become increasingly apparent... In order to effectively regulate and address the issues, there needs to be a concerted effort involving doctors, academicians, lawyers, religious authorities and relevant government agencies to contribute their knowledge and expertise towards the development of a pragmatic and viable advance directive model in Malaysia, as well as to educate legislators and the general public on the importance and use of advance directives so as to facilitate statutory reform.”

Word count: 16,305 words

⁶⁶ Palliative care has sometimes been accused of *medicalising* death (O'Mahony, 2016, p.140). However, one can argue that a certain degree of medicalisation is necessary because prescribing the correct drugs for the relief of distressing symptoms are skills that doctors bring to the care of the dying. The real problem is when dying is *over-medicalised*.

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Appendix A
Example of an Advance Directive

Advance Directive for Health Care

Name:
Address:
Hospital unit number:

It is my express wish that if I should develop

- (a) senile, severe degenerative brain disease (due to Alzheimer's disease, arterial disease, AIDS, or other agency or
- (b) serious brain damage resulting from accidental or other injury or illness or
- (c) advanced or terminal malignant disease or
- (d) severely incapacitating and progressive degenerative disease of the nerves or muscles

and have become mentally incompetent to express my opinion about accepting or declining life sustaining treatment, and if two independent physicians conclude that, to the best of current medical knowledge, my condition is irreversible then the following points should be taken into consideration:

- In the event of a cardiac arrest, regardless of the cause, I should not be given cardiopulmonary resuscitation
- Any separate illness-for example, pneumonia or a heart or kidney condition- that may threaten my life should not be given active treatment unless it appears to be causing me undue physical suffering
- During such an advanced illness, if I should become unable to swallow food, fluid, or medication then these should not be given by any artificial means except to relieve obvious suffering
- During such an illness, if my condition deteriorates without reversible cause, and as a result my behaviour becomes violent, noisy, or in other ways degrading, or if I appear to be suffering severe pain, then any such symptoms should be controlled with suitable drug treatment, regardless of the consequences on my physical health and my survival, within the extent of the law.
- Other requests:

The object of this directive is to minimise distress or indignity which I may suffer or create during an incurable illness, and to spare my medical advisers or relatives, or both, the burden of making difficult decisions on my behalf.

Signed:
Date:

Witness 1:
Witness 2:

Statement by one witness: I declare that in my opinion the above person is of sound mind.

Signed:
Date:

Source:

Robertson, G.S., 1995. Making an advance directive. *British Medical Journal*, 310, p.237.

Appendix B
Example of a POLST Form- Front Page

HIPAA PERMITS DISCLOSURE OF POLST TO OTHER HEALTH CARE PROVIDERS AS NECESSARY				
 EMSA #111 B (Effective 1/1/2016)*	Physician Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment (POLST)			
	First follow these orders, then contact Physician/NP/PA. A copy of the signed POLST form is a legally valid physician order. Any section not completed implies full treatment for that section. POLST complements an Advance Directive and is not intended to replace that document.		Patient Last Name: _____	Date Form Prepared: _____
			Patient First Name: _____	Patient Date of Birth: _____
			Patient Middle Name: _____	Medical Record #: (optional) _____
A	CARDIOPULMONARY RESUSCITATION (CPR): <i>If patient has no pulse and is not breathing. If patient is NOT in cardiopulmonary arrest, follow orders in Sections B and C.</i>			
Check One	<input type="checkbox"/> Attempt Resuscitation/CPR (Selecting CPR in Section A requires selecting Full Treatment in Section B)			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Do Not Attempt Resuscitation/DNR (Allow Natural Death)			
B	MEDICAL INTERVENTIONS: <i>If patient is found with a pulse and/or is breathing.</i>			
Check One	<input type="checkbox"/> Full Treatment – primary goal of prolonging life by all medically effective means. In addition to treatment described in Selective Treatment and Comfort-Focused Treatment, use intubation, advanced airway interventions, mechanical ventilation, and cardioversion as indicated.			
	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Trial Period of Full Treatment.</i>			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Selective Treatment – goal of treating medical conditions while avoiding burdensome measures. In addition to treatment described in Comfort-Focused Treatment, use medical treatment, IV antibiotics, and IV fluids as indicated. Do not intubate. May use non-invasive positive airway pressure. Generally avoid intensive care.			
	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Request transfer to hospital only if comfort needs cannot be met in current location.</i>			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Comfort-Focused Treatment – primary goal of maximizing comfort. Relieve pain and suffering with medication by any route as needed; use oxygen, suctioning, and manual treatment of airway obstruction. Do not use treatments listed in Full and Selective Treatment unless consistent with comfort goal. Request transfer to hospital only if comfort needs cannot be met in current location.			
	Additional Orders: _____			
C	ARTIFICIALLY ADMINISTERED NUTRITION: <i>Offer food by mouth if feasible and desired.</i>			
Check One	<input type="checkbox"/> Long-term artificial nutrition, including feeding tubes. Additional Orders: _____			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Trial period of artificial nutrition, including feeding tubes. _____			
	<input type="checkbox"/> No artificial means of nutrition, including feeding tubes. _____			
D	INFORMATION AND SIGNATURES:			
	Discussed with: <input type="checkbox"/> Patient (Patient Has Capacity) <input type="checkbox"/> Legally Recognized Decisionmaker			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Advance Directive dated _____, available and reviewed →		Health Care Agent if named in Advance Directive:	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Advance Directive not available		Name: _____	
	<input type="checkbox"/> No Advance Directive		Phone: _____	
Signature of Physician / Nurse Practitioner / Physician Assistant (Physician/NP/PA)				
My signature below indicates to the best of my knowledge that these orders are consistent with the patient's medical condition and preferences.				
Print Physician/NP/PA Name: _____		Physician/NP/PA Phone #: _____	Physician/PA License #, NP Cert. #: _____	
Physician/NP/PA Signature: (required) _____		Date: _____		
Signature of Patient or Legally Recognized Decisionmaker				
I am aware that this form is voluntary. By signing this form, the legally recognized decisionmaker acknowledges that this request regarding resuscitative measures is consistent with the known desires of, and with the best interest of, the individual who is the subject of the form.				
Print Name: _____		Relationship: (write self if patient) _____		
Signature: (required) _____		Date: _____		
Mailing Address (street/city/state/zip): _____		Phone Number: _____		
SEND FORM WITH PATIENT WHENEVER TRANSFERRED OR DISCHARGED				

*Form versions with effective dates of 1/1/2009, 4/1/2011 or 10/1/2014 are also valid

Example of a POLST Form- Back Page

HIPAA PERMITS DISCLOSURE OF POLST TO OTHER HEALTH CARE PROVIDERS AS NECESSARY		
Patient Information		
Name (last, first, middle):	Date of Birth:	Gender: M F
NP/PA's Supervising Physician		Preparer Name (if other than signing Physician/NP/PA)
Name:	Name/Title:	Phone #:
Additional Contact <input type="checkbox"/> None		
Name:	Relationship to Patient:	Phone #:
Directions for Health Care Provider		
Completing POLST		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completing a POLST form is voluntary. California law requires that a POLST form be followed by healthcare providers, and provides immunity to those who comply in good faith. In the hospital setting, a patient will be assessed by a physician, or a nurse practitioner (NP) or a physician assistant (PA) acting under the supervision of the physician, who will issue appropriate orders that are consistent with the patient's preferences. • POLST does not replace the Advance Directive. When available, review the Advance Directive and POLST form to ensure consistency, and update forms appropriately to resolve any conflicts. • POLST must be completed by a health care provider based on patient preferences and medical indications. • A legally recognized decisionmaker may include a court-appointed conservator or guardian, agent designated in an Advance Directive, orally designated surrogate, spouse, registered domestic partner, parent of a minor, closest available relative, or person whom the patient's physician/NP/PA believes best knows what is in the patient's best interest and will make decisions in accordance with the patient's expressed wishes and values to the extent known. • A legally recognized decisionmaker may execute the POLST form only if the patient lacks capacity or has designated that the decisionmaker's authority is effective immediately. • To be valid a POLST form must be signed by (1) a physician, or by a nurse practitioner or a physician assistant acting under the supervision of a physician and within the scope of practice authorized by law and (2) the patient or decisionmaker. Verbal orders are acceptable with follow-up signature by physician/NP/PA in accordance with facility/community policy. • If a translated form is used with patient or decisionmaker, attach it to the signed English POLST form. • Use of original form is strongly encouraged. Photocopies and FAXes of signed POLST forms are legal and valid. A copy should be retained in patient's medical record, on Ultra Pink paper when possible. 		
Using POLST		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any incomplete section of POLST implies full treatment for that section. <p>Section A:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If found pulseless and not breathing, no defibrillator (including automated external defibrillators) or chest compressions should be used on a patient who has chosen "Do Not Attempt Resuscitation." <p>Section B:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When comfort cannot be achieved in the current setting, the patient, including someone with "Comfort-Focused Treatment," should be transferred to a setting able to provide comfort (e.g., treatment of a hip fracture). • Non-invasive positive airway pressure includes continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP), bi-level positive airway pressure (BiPAP), and bag valve mask (BVM) assisted respirations. • IV antibiotics and hydration generally are not "Comfort-Focused Treatment." • Treatment of dehydration prolongs life. If a patient desires IV fluids, indicate "Selective Treatment" or "Full Treatment." • Depending on local EMS protocol, "Additional Orders" written in Section B may not be implemented by EMS personnel. 		
Reviewing POLST		
It is recommended that POLST be reviewed periodically. Review is recommended when:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The patient is transferred from one care setting or care level to another, or • There is a substantial change in the patient's health status, or • The patient's treatment preferences change. 		
Modifying and Voiding POLST		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A patient with capacity can, at any time, request alternative treatment or revoke a POLST by any means that indicates intent to revoke. It is recommended that revocation be documented by drawing a line through Sections A through D, writing "VOID" in large letters, and signing and dating this line. • A legally recognized decisionmaker may request to modify the orders, in collaboration with the physician/NP/PA, based on the known desires of the patient or, if unknown, the patient's best interests. 		
This form is approved by the California Emergency Medical Services Authority in cooperation with the statewide POLST Task Force. For more information or a copy of the form, visit www.caPOLST.org .		
SEND FORM WITH PATIENT WHENEVER TRANSFERRED OR DISCHARGED		

Source:

California Emergency Medical Services Authority, 2016. *Physician Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment (POLST)*. Available at: <http://capolst.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/2016_CA_POLST_English.pdf> Accessed 16 September 2016).

Appendix C
Example of a Statement of Wishes and Values

Statement of Wishes and Values for a Christian Believer

I recognise that my current illness is unlikely to be cured and that it is likely to lead to my death. As a Christian believer, this is not something that I fear. I look forward to going to be with Jesus Christ, who has promised me eternal life through his death and resurrection. I know he will be with me to comfort and support me whatever the future holds.

I am grateful for the medical and nursing care I am receiving at this time of need. I would like to be actively involved in all decisions both about my care and about those individuals and agencies that are involved in my care.

Where it is possible, I wish to be consulted about all decisions relevant to my care and participate in those decisions. However, if I should ever lose the ability to participate actively in decision-making, I would like the following principles to be respected when decisions need to be made:

I would like to be kept as free from pain and other distressing symptoms as possible.

I would like to retain the ability to communicate with family and friends, if at all possible, and not to be given treatment intended to reduce my level of consciousness unnecessarily.

I would never want to receive intervention or treatment designed to end my life, regardless of how my level of suffering may be perceived by others.

(Optional sentence) In the case of an acute deterioration in my condition, I would like to receive active medical treatment that has a reasonable chance of prolonging my life and preserving function.

(Optional sentence) I would wish to receive clinically assisted nutrition and/or hydration if these have a reasonable chance of prolonging my life or of alleviating my symptoms and if they are not causing me evident distress.

If my condition is deteriorating irretrievably, and in the view of the medical and nursing teams looking after me, there is no realistic hope of recovery, I would accept and welcome palliative treatment instead of further attempts at active medical management.

I would not want to cling on to life in this world because I have a living hope of life after death and of a wonderful future with my Lord Jesus Christ.

My life as part of a local church community is very important to me. I would not wish my church friends to be denied access from visiting me. In particular, I value on-going spiritual and personal support from my church leaders and from other friends, including the following named individuals:
..... If I am ever unable to participate in decisions about my care, I wish the following named individuals to be actively involved in the decision-making process:

Signed:

Witnessed:

Date:

Source:

Wyatt, J., 2015. *Right to die?* Nottingham: Inter-Varsity Press. pp.160-161.

Appendix D

Guidance and Safeguards Pertaining to End-of-Life Care in the UK

In addition to the MCA, the CoP, and the Explanatory Notes, there are other Guidance and Safeguards that have been issued by other relevant UK authorities. This list is not exhaustive, but the following are worth a mention:

- (1) *End of Life Care Strategy: Promoting high quality care for all adults at the end of life* (2008) by the Department of Health (DoH).
- (2) *Treatment and care towards the end of life: Good practice in decision making* (2010) by the General Medical Council (GMC).
- (3) *Capacity, care planning and advance care planning in life limiting illness: A Guide for Health and Social Care Staff* (2014) by the NHS Improving Quality.
- (4) *Advance decisions to refuse treatment: A guide for health and social care professionals* (2014) by the National Council for Palliative Care and the NHS Improving Quality.

Appendix E

Summary of Findings from the Study on Views of Older Malaysians on Advanced Directives and Advanced Care Planning

- (1) None of the respondents had ever heard of ACP/AD or its concept, nor had they made any firm decisions regarding their future medical management should they become seriously ill.
- (2) The majority of respondents did not seem to understand the severity of their illness.
- (3) A majority of respondents agreed that their attending doctor should initiate discussions on their end-of-life care.
- (4) While half of the respondents would consider making plans for future management, most of them agreed that a verbal discussion would suffice.
- (5) Despite receiving explanation about the purpose of ADs, a third did not wish to make any written ADs.
- (6) Family members, mainly the patients' children, were the surrogate decision maker of choice.
- (7) A majority of respondents did not have any preferences as to whether they would like to receive medical care if they were dying.
- (8) 5 respondents welcomed life-prolonging treatment despite there being no hope of recovery.
- (9) The majority of respondents agreed that their views were influenced by their religion.
- (10) The majority of respondents stated that it would be best to leave their future to fate or God.

Source:

Htut, Y., Shahrul, K. and Poi, P.J.H., 2007. The Views of Older Malaysians on Advanced Directive and Advanced Care Planning: A Qualitative Study. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Public Health*, 19, pp.58-66.

Appendix F

List of Basic Requirements for Regulating AdvDecs in Malaysia

- (1) The *conditions as to the validity and applicability of advance directives*. This includes the need for prior consultation with a doctor and a prerequisite for advance directives to specify in clear terms as to when the instructions would be operative.
- (2) The *factors to determine whether the person is competent*. This would be relevant during the process of drawing up the advance directive and at the time when doctors need to decide whether to put the advance directive into effect.
- (3) *Any restriction as to what an advance directive may contain*. For example, the MCA CoP (UK) 2007 states that an advance directive cannot include a refusal to be provided basic care such as warmth, shelter, actions to keep a person clean and the offer of food and water by mouth, although artificial nutrition and hydration may be refused.
- (4) *A scheme to verify that the person has been provided with adequate information during advance care planning and to record the values which are held by the patient to be significant in forming decisions*.
- (5) *A system to facilitate the safekeeping and retrieval of advance directives*.
- (6) *The means by which an advance directive may be revoked and whether it may be done partially without affecting the applicability of the advance directive to other circumstances in the future*.
- (7) *The measures to be taken in the event that an advance directive is found to be ineffective or its validity and/or applicability are disputed*. This also requires the need for a guideline indicating how the best interests of the patient should be determined, and reference to a judicial forum in order to obtain a declaration affirming that the doctor's choice of action is legally justified.
- (8) *The appointment of a health care proxy, including the instrument by which he is to be appointed, the scope of appointment and circumstances in which his authority may be overridden*.
- (9) *The legal effect of an advance directive and its limitations*. It is important that the legislative and/or regulatory instrument contain provision(s) expressly stating that compliance with a valid advance directive will absolve the doctor from liability. It may also include limitation of liability in other circumstances. Further, an advance directive cannot authorise any act that would be contrary to existing law.
- (10) *The patient's religious principles to be considered in the implementation of advance directives*.

Source:

Kassim, P.N.J. and Alias, F., 2015a. Advance Directives for Medical treatment: The Current Legal Status. *Malayan Law Journal*, 3, pp.1-20.

~How people die remains in the memory of those who live on~
Dame Cicely Saunders
Founder of the Modern Hospice Movement